

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialization of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D8.1 - Sustainability performance (LCA) and cost assessment

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
Al	Aluminium
AM	Active Material
BMS	Battery Management System
BOM	Bill of Materials
C45	Carbon
CAM	Cathode Active Material
Co	Cobalt
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
Cu	Copper
DDP	Digital Data Platform
EV	Electric Vehicles
FU	Functional Unit
GWP	Global warming Potential
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
Li	Lithium
LIB	Lithium-ion Batteries
Li-M	Lithium-Metal
MFCA	Material Flow Cost Assessment
MMS	Module Management System
Mn	Manganese
Ni	Nickel
Pt	Ecopoints
SoA	State-of-Art
SSB	Solid-State Battery/Solid-State-Batteries
U.S.	United States
WP	Work Package

Some of the sensitive information in this public deliverable is only available in the separate document titled ANNEX 1 and provided to the Project Officer directly for reference purposes.

Contents

Executive Summary.....	11
Introduction	13
SPINMATE - Sustainability performance and cost assessment methodology.....	16
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	16
Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA)	21
State-of-art analysis	23
Environmental SoA	24
NMC111	33
NMC622	35
NMC811	37
Costs SoA	39
NMC 111	45
NMC 622	47
NMC 811	49
Comparison of the baseline results.....	51
SPINMATE small-scale cell components development processes.....	53
NMC powder production	54
Lithium-Metal anode production	56
Cathode wet processing	57
Cathode dry processing	59
Electrolyte production	60
Results and discussion	61
Environmental Assessment	61
NMC powder production	62
Lithium-Metal anode production.....	63
Cathode wet processing.....	64
Cathode dry processing.....	66
Electrolyte production	67
Cost Assessment	70
NMC powder production	70
Lithium-Metal anode production.....	71
Cathode wet processing.....	72
Cathode dry processing.....	72
Electrolyte production	73
Conclusions	75
References	80
Annexes.....	84
Life Cycle Inventory	84
Baseline.....	84

Life Cycle Impact Assessment results	90
Baseline	90
SPINMATE's cell components process results.....	102

List of Figures

Figure 1 - LCA framework.	17
Figure 2 - Data collection workflow.....	18
Figure 3 - Approach to assess environmental and cost project results.....	23
Figure 4 - Number of publications per FU.	28
Figure 5 - Number of publications per impact method.	29
Figure 6 - Share of the global Li-ion battery manufacturing capacity in 2021 [3].....	31
Figure 7 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack in Pt.....	33
Figure 8 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery cell in Pt.....	34
Figure 9 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack in Pt.....	35
Figure 10 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery cell in Pt.....	36
Figure 11 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack in Pt.....	37
Figure 12 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery cell in Pt.....	38
Figure 13 - Scheme of the strategy for the cost baseline.	43
Figure 14 - Distribution of total costs for NMC 111. NMC 622. and NMC 811.	51
Figure 15 - Process flow of the NMC811 fabrication process.	55
Figure 16 - Process flow of the Li-M anode.	56
Figure 17 - Process flow of the wet cathode processing.	58
Figure 18 - Process flow of the dry cathode processing.....	59
Figure 19 - Process flow of the electrolyte processing.....	60
Figure 20 - Potential environmental impacts of NMC811 powder production in Pt (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	62
Figure 21 - Potential environmental impacts of Li-M anode production in Pt (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	63
Figure 22 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	64
Figure 23 - Potential environmental impacts of mixing step for cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H);.....	65
Figure 24 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing in Pt (FU = 0.3 kg) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	66
Figure 25 - Potential environmental impacts of mixing step for cathode dry processing in Pt (FU = 0.3 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	67
Figure 26 - Potential environmental impacts of Electrolyte production in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).	68
Figure 27 - Potential environmental impacts of Solubilization step in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).	68
Figure 28 - Potential environmental impacts of mixing step in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	69
Figure 29 - Cost preliminary results NMC powder production (FU = 1 kg 557.96 €/kg).	71

Figure 30 - Cost preliminary results of anode Li-M production (FU = 1 kg | 1150.45 €/kg). ..71

Figure 31 - Cost preliminary results of cathode wet fabrication (FU = 1 kg | 720.40 €/kg)...72

Figure 32 - Cost preliminary results of cathode dry fabrication (FU = 1 kg | 542.43 €/kg).....73

Figure 33 - Cost preliminary results of Electrolyte membrane production (FU = 1 kg | 55.70 €/kg).74

Figure 34 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....93

Figure 35 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....97

Figure 36 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....101

Figure 37 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC powder fabrication (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....104

Figure 38 - Contributions to each impact category of Li-M anode production (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....107

Figure 39 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 g) - ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H);110

Figure 40 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing (FU = 0.3 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....113

Figure 41- Potential environmental impacts of electrolyte production (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).116

List of Tables

Table 1 - LCA methodology for SPINMATE project.....	18
Table 2 - Description of the impact categories assessed in this study for ReCiPe 2016 [6]....	19
Table 3 – MFCA methodology overview [9].	21
Table 4 – Literature search of LCA studies on NMC batteries.....	25
Table 5 - CO ₂ eq/kWh emissions of battery manufacturing (per cradle-to-gate) [15], [16], [22], [24].....	29
Table 6 - GHG emissions (KgCO ₂ -eq/kWh) of the production of LIBs [25], [33].	30
Table 7 - LCA methodology for the baseline.....	30
Table 8 - Literature search of cost studies on Lithium batteries.	40
Table 9 - Costs methodology for the baseline.....	42
Table 10 – Percentage of wastes considered per cell component indicated in BatPaC Database.	44
Table 11 - MFCA inputs at cell-level for NMC 111 for the cost baseline.....	45
Table 12 - MFCA inputs at module-level for NMC 111 for the cost baseline.....	46
Table 13 – MFCA inputs at pack-level for NMC 111 for the cost baseline.....	46
Table 14 - MFCA inputs at cell-level for NMC 622 for the cost baseline.....	47
Table 15 - MFCA inputs at module-level for NMC 622 for the cost baseline.....	48
Table 16 - MFCA inputs at pack-level for NMC 622 for the cost baseline.....	48
Table 17 - MFCA inputs at cell-level for NMC 811 for the cost baseline.....	49
Table 18 – MFCA inputs at module-level for NMC 811 for the cost baseline.	50
Table 19 - MFCA inputs at pack-level for NMC 811 for the cost baseline.....	50
Table 20 - Overview of the cost baseline results at pack-level for the FU of 100kWh.	51
Table 21 – Overview of the cost baseline results for the FU of 1 kWh.	51
Table 22 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC111 battery pack [18].....	84
Table 23 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC111 battery cell [18].....	85
Table 24 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC622 battery pack [18].....	86
Table 25 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC622 battery cell [18].....	87
Table 26 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC811 battery pack [18].....	88
Table 27 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC811 battery cell [18].....	89
Table 28 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).	90
Table 29 -Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery cell in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).	91
Table 30 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack (numerical) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....	92
Table 31 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).	94
Table 32 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery cell in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).	95

Table 33 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack (numerical) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....	96
Table 34 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	98
Table 35 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery cell in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	99
Table 36 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....	100
Table 37 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC powder fabrication in pt (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) (numeric).....	102
Table 38 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC powder fabrication (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).....	103
Table 39 - Potential environmental impacts of Li-M anode production in mPt (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) (numerical).....	105
Table 40 - Contributions to each impact category of Li-M anode production (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).....	106
Table 41 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 g) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	108
Table 42 Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing (FU = 527.79 g) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).....	109
Table 43 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing in Pt (FU = 0.3 kg) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	111
Table 44 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing (FU = 0.3 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).....	112
Table 45 - Potential environmental impacts of electrolyte production in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).....	114
Table 46 - Potential environmental impacts of electrolyte production (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).....	115

Executive Summary

This document aims to report the environmental and cost assessment of SPINMATE's activities. The analysis focuses on the activities conducted in Work Package 3 (WP3) related to the production of the Solid-State Battery (SSB) cell components: anode, cathode, and electrolyte.

To comprehensively assess the environmental impacts of the SSB cell components, a life cycle inventory (LCI) was developed based on primary data collected from SPINMATE's partners with the support of the Digital Data Platform (DDP)- **SUNDIAL**, which enables the gathering of data safely and confidentially. Since the focus of the SPINMATE project is the pilot-line, a cradle-to-gate approach was considered. The study focused on assessing each cell component production phase individually in order to identify, from the early development stage, environment and cost hotspots. The environmental assessment followed the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology according to the ISO 14040/10044 standards [1].

The impacts were quantified and characterized using the ReCiPe v1.1 impact method, and Ecoinvent v3.9.1 was the database used.

Regarding the environmental assessment, the results indicated that:

- The anode production process - lithium (Li) deposition step is the main impact contributor, primarily due to the high consumption of copper (Cu) compared to Li. Energy consumption data is currently unavailable as the specific coating material has not been chosen, which will directly influence the energy requirements. Consequently, the assessment does not include environmental impacts related to energy use;
- The cathode wet processing - the main impact contributors are the mixing and the drying steps. The significant impact of the mixing process is mainly due to the materials used in the Cathode Active Material (CAM) NMC811, related to the cobalt (Co) and nickel (Ni);
- The cathode dry processing - the mixing step is the main impact contributor. This result is mainly due to the consumption of NMC811, more precisely, due to Co and Ni;
- The electrolyte production - the main impact contributors are the solubilization and the mixing steps. Solubilization is the main impact contributor in 11 impact categories, followed by mixing. Energy consumption is the main impact contributor for both steps.

The cost assessment followed the Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA) methodology, which focuses on tracking the material and energy flows and their associated costs throughout the production process, supported by ISO 14051 standards [2]. In this way, the cost assessment is able to pinpoint the main contributors in the process, thus enabling the identification of potential improvement paths. For this, the flows and costs were collected from SPINMATE's partners, also with the support of DDP - SUNDIAL. In line with the environmental assessment, the chosen boundaries for the cost analysis are also cradle-to-gate, focusing on individually assessing each cell component production phase. The quantification and characterization of the impacts have been carried out using adjusted data from BatPaC 5.1 Databased.

In the cost assessment, it was noted that:

- The anode production process - the Li deposition step is the main cost contributor, representing 97% of total costs. This can be attributed to the introduction of Li into the system;
- The cathode wet processing - the mixing step stands out as the main contributor to total costs, accounting for 90% of it. This is attributed to the utilisation of NMC811 and catholyte materials;

- The cathode dry processing – the mixing step is the main contributor to the costs, with contribution of 77%. Other than that, the extrusion step also has an important contribution (22%). These are justified by the introduction of NMC811 and catholyte, respectively;
- The electrolyte production – the solubilisation step emerges as the main cost driver, followed by the mixing step. Solubilisation contributes 47% to the total step costs, while mixing accounts for 30%. Both steps are primarily driven by energy consumption.

Initially, an analysis of the current State of the Art (SoA) of the potential competing technologies was carried out. For this analysis, China was considered for the baseline, since it is the world's leading manufacturer of batteries [3]. This analysis aimed to identify cost and environmental hotspots that could lead to potential issues, gaps, and risks. Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) with similar chemistry to the SPINMATE were selected for the baseline and an environmental analysis with the same database and method was performed for an adequate correlation with the SoA.

Correlating the SPINMATE results with the selected baseline at the cell component level revealed that, in the environmental assessment of cathode production, the active materials (AM), particularly cobalt (Co) and nickel (Ni), are the main contributors to the cathode's environmental impact. This commonality was observed both in the SPINMATE's results and in the SoA. In the case of the cost assessment, the correlation shows that, although the cathode production process contributes significantly to the total cost and is the main contributor in the baseline and in the SoA, in the case of the project results for 1 kg of cathode and 1 kg of anode, the anode has more associated costs.

Introduction

With the ambition of a prosperous, equitable-fair society and a resource-efficient, competitive economy, Europe has made substantial commitments towards sustainability, particularly aiming for climate neutrality by 2050 [4]. Addressing greenhouse gas emissions in the transport sector stands out as a must. With a focus on electrifying the transport sector, Europe is transitioning from fossil fuels to battery-powered vehicles. Batteries assume a pivotal role as an energy source, supporting sustainable development, enabling green mobility, and contributing to the goal of climate neutrality.

To ensure that the European Union's (EU) products contribute to global carbon emission reduction, it's imperative that products available in the EU are sourced and **manufactured sustainably**. This guarantees that the negative impact of products sold and marketed within Europe is minimised, thereby supporting broader initiatives to combat climate change globally.

Recognising this need for sustainable manufactured batteries, the European Commission actively supports and invests in research, innovation, and collaboration efforts to drive the development and **production of sustainable batteries for Electric Vehicles (EV)**. An example of this initiative is the SPINMATE project.

SPINMATE stands for scalable and sustainable pilot line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries (SSB) for the automotive sector. It aims to develop an innovative, scalable, safe and cost-effective digital-driven proof-of-concept manufacturing pilot line.

SPINMATE intends to manufacture small 1 Ah and large 10 Ah SSB cells with NMC811-based cathode, Li-Metal (Li-M) anode, and solid-state electrolyte based on a polymer and Li salt. This new technology seeks to ensure:

- Enhanced energy densities, overcoming current Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) limitations;
- Improved safety in both solutions and workers;
- Increased sustainable mass production;
- Decreased carbon footprint and cost.

To demonstrate the sustainability and the economic competitiveness of the SPINMATE proof-of-concept pilot line within WP8, a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and cost analysis will be undertaken (Result 16) alongside a recycling plan (Result 17). WP8 will conduct the environmental and cost assessments of SPINMATE's advancements throughout the project duration, aiming to measure its environmental impacts and costs quantitatively. These evaluations provide helpful insights to cell manufacturers, supporting informed decision-making processes.

This deliverable aims to present the life cycle environmental and cost performance of SSB small— and large-scale cell prototypes, with the support of the developed Digital Data Platform (DDP)—SUNDIAL. It contains the preliminary environmental and cost assessment of SPINMATE's initial developments in WP3. These developments are related to the battery cell component level (anode, cathode, and electrolyte).

This report corresponds to the first evaluation of the environmental and economic technical activities conducted regarding the development of the innovative SSB cell pilot-line. This assessment focuses on analysing the operational processes conducted in WP3 related to the development and optimization of cell formulations and components.

The results of this first evaluation indicate the environmental and cost performance of the work conducted so far and contribute to:

- Identification of potential areas of improvements: despite these processes being at lab-scale level, this allows early identification of hotspots and potential future limitations (production processes, material sourcing, recycling methods);
- Support the decision-making process: Inform and support the battery cell developers. By clarifying the impacts, consumptions, and costs of their processes, battery cell developers will make smarter decisions. Examples include analysing and comparing different SSB designs, manufacturing processes, sources of resources, or end-of-life strategies;
- Correlation with existing technologies: indicates whether the technology's performance aligns with that of current market technologies.

These assessments were conducted with the support of standards and methodologies internationally accepted, following specific and concise guidelines to grant a robust and reliable assessment. The environmental assessment followed the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) based on the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards [1], [5]. It is a useful tool to assess the environmental impact of a product, service, or process. It involves systematically evaluating the inputs and outputs (material and energy flows) associated with each life cycle stage (resource extraction, manufacturing, distribution, use, and end-of-life). The cost assessment follows the Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA) methodology based on the ISO 14051 standard [2]. MFCA is a management tool used to assess and optimize material and energy flows in industrial processes by quantifying the costs associated with material and energy consumption. MFCA helps businesses to identify areas for cost reduction and resource efficiency improvements.

Additionally, an analysis of the current State-Of-Art (SoA) technologies present in the market was conducted. The analyses of the current SoA allow a correlation between the environmental and cost performance of the new product and existing technologies, serving as a baseline for evaluating potential improvements and identifying areas of optimisation. For SPINMATE technology, the SoA analysis focused on current batteries with similar chemistries, such as NMC111, NMC622, and NMC811. The study focused on identifying potential environmental implications and costs associated with these chemistries related to their production phase, material sourcing, etc.

This deliverable is organized as follows:

- Introduction: This section provides an overview of the deliverable's objectives and contributions to the SPINMATE project, as well as a brief introduction to the work conducted for the environmental and cost assessment;
- SPINMATE – Sustainability performance and cost assessment methodology: Describes the methodologies applied to study the environmental and cost performance of SPINMATE's current developments, including the defined goal and scope, functional unit, and system boundaries;
- State-of-Art analysis: presents the current state of technologies in the market that SPINMATE aims to surpass, identifying the main gaps and challenges;
- SPINMATE small-scale cell components development processes: presents the production process flows of each cell component by each step;
- Results and discussion: this section presents the results of the performance of each cell component, either environmental or cost;

- **Conclusions:** Summarizes the main conclusions for each component process flow, relating them to the state-of-the-art and highlighting limitations;
- **References:** Lists the references used to support the evidences;
- **Annexes:** contains more detailed results regarding the baseline modelling and preliminary results from SPINMATE's developments.

SPINMATE - Sustainability performance and cost assessment methodology

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

According to ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a comprehensive methodology used to evaluate the environmental aspects and potential impacts associated with a product, process, or service throughout its life cycle stages. This assessment considers inputs and outputs (resource use, energy consumption, air and water emissions, and potential waste generation) across all stages, including raw material extraction, production, distribution, use, and end-of-life [1], [5].

This methodology can support in:

Identifying opportunities to enhance the environmental performance of products/processes/systems at various points in their life cycle

Providing valuable insights for decision-makers in industry, government, or non-government organisations (e.g., for the purpose of strategic planning, priority setting, product or process design, or redesign)

Selection of appropriate metrics for assessing environmental performance, which includes selecting relevant indicators and measurement methods

Marketing (Promotional activities, such as introducing an eco-labelling program, asserting environmental attributes, or creating an environmental product declaration)

LCA takes into consideration environmental elements and potential impacts (like resource consumption and environmental effects) across all stages of a product's lifecycle from raw material acquisition through production, use, end-of-life treatment, recycling, and final disposal (i.e., cradle-to-grave). To conduct a life cycle study, it is necessary to take into consideration four phases (Figure 1):

1. The goal and scope definition;
2. The inventory analysis phase;
3. The impact assessment phase;
4. The interpretation phase.

Figure 1 - LCA framework.

The interpretation phase of an LCA can occur in other stages, even if the assessment is still ongoing. Particularly in more complex LCAs, ongoing interpretation of results aids in refining the analysis as it progresses. Occasionally, revisiting earlier stages to integrate new insights, which then inform subsequent phases, is necessary.

Phase 1: The goal and scope

The **goal** definition consists of defining the intended application, the reasons for carrying out the study, the target audience, and whether the results are planned to be used in comparative assertions to be disclosed to the public.

The **scope** definition involves detailing and defining the product/system to be studied, the boundaries, and the assumptions of the study. It encompasses specifying the functions of the product system, functional unit, determining the processes and inputs to be included (system boundary) and establishing the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) methodology and indicators to be evaluated. Additionally, the data quality requirements, assumptions and limitations must be clarified.

The **Functional Unit (FU)** is a quantifiable measure that defines the function or service provided by the product or system being assessed. It serves as a reference unit for comparing environmental impacts between different products or systems. The functional unit may vary depending on the goal and scope of the LCA but typically represents the unit of product output or the service provided by the product.

The **system boundary** defines which processes and inputs are included in the assessment. It can consider all stages of the product or system's life cycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal or recycling. The system boundary may vary depending on the goal and scope of the LCA but typically includes all relevant processes and inputs that contribute to the environmental impacts associated with the product or system under study.

- Cradle-to-grave: it considers the entire life cycle, from resource extraction, transport/distribution, manufacturing, use and end-of-life;
- Cradle-to-gate: it considers the partial life cycle since resource extraction, transport/distribution, and manufacturing are involved. It's more used when the focus is on the manufacturing process;
- Well-to-wheel: it's more used for vehicle analysis and helps to reflect different efficiencies and emissions of energy technologies and fuels in the upstream and downstream stages.

The **LCIA methodology and indicators** evaluate the potential environmental impacts associated with the life cycle stages of a product, process, or service. LCIA involves characterising and quantifying these impacts using impact categories and indicators. The choice of the LCIA methodology and indicators must be in line with the study's objectives.

For this deliverable, the goal and scope are presented in Table 1:

Table 1 - LCA methodology for SPINMATE project.

Phase of the study	Description
<i>Goal and Scope</i>	This deliverable aims to report the life cycle environmental and cost performance of SPINMATE's initial results with the support of the matured digital data platform. This is done in the scope of the European Project - SPINMATE.
<i>Functional Unit</i>	With the project's current development, these results will be assessed per cell component produced: one anode produced, one cathode produced, and one electrolyte produced. Once there isn't a fully developed technology, the baseline and the initial results of SPINMATE will be correlated but not directly compared.
<i>Boundaries</i>	Cradle-to-gate. This study focuses on assessing a pilot manufacturing line for SSB cells, so it was found relevant to consider cradle-to-gate boundaries. No initial results are available for the SPINMATE's recycling process. Therefore, this aspect will be considered in the next evaluation phase.

Phase 2: Inventory analysis

This phase consists of compiling data related to the inputs (e.g., materials, energy) and outputs (e.g., emissions, and waste) regarding each stage of the product's life cycle. This phase requires collecting data from various sources, such as suppliers, manufacturers, and databases. The necessary data for the assessments was done with the support of SUNDIAL. The data collection workflow is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Data collection workflow.

The LCA flowchart is created in SUNDIAL with partners. The responsible partner inserts the data for the flowchart. Subsequently, INEGI analyses the quality of the data and asks for adjustments if necessary. After that, the environmental and cost assessment is conducted, and results are provided. Due to confidential concerns, the LCI of SPINMATE's processes is in the annexes.

Phase 3: Impact assessment

The impact assessment phase consists of evaluating the potential environmental impacts associated with the inputs and outputs identified during the inventory analysis phase. This assessment typically includes the characterisation and quantification of these impacts using impact categories and indicators. Impact assessment allows the comparison of different environmental impacts across various life cycle stages and helps stakeholders identify priority areas for improvement and decision-making. The results of the impact assessment provide valuable insights into the environmental performance of the product or process under study, guiding efforts towards sustainability and resource efficiency. Table 2 presents the impact categories to be used in the environmental performance.

Table 2 - Description of the impact categories assessed in this study for ReCiPe 2016 [6].

Impact Category	Description
Climate change	The Global warming potential, as outlined in the IPCC 2013 report, measures the overall increase in infrared radiative forcing caused by a greenhouse gas (GHG) over a 100-year period, using the hierarchical perspective. This potential is quantified in terms of kilograms of CO2 equivalents.
Ozone depletion	The depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer caused by human-made emissions of ozone-depleting substances (ODS) is measured in kilograms of CFC-11 equivalents.
Ionizing radiation	The level of exposure for the global population, based on the collective dose resulting from the emission of a radionuclide, is measured in kilobecquerels of Cobalt-60 equivalents released into the air.
Fine particulate matter formation	Intake fraction of PM2.5 is measured in kilograms of PM2.5 equivalents.
Photochemical ozone formation terrestrial ecosystems	The change in ozone intake rate due to variations in precursor emissions (NOx and NMVOC) is measured in kilograms of NOx equivalents.
Photochemical ozone formation. human health	The alteration in ozone intake rate resulting from changes in precursor emissions (NOx and NMVOC) is measured in kilograms of NOx equivalents.
Terrestrial acidification	Acidification Potential (AP), determined using the emission-weighted world average fate factor of SO2, is expressed in kilograms of SO2 equivalents.
Freshwater eutrophication,	The environmental persistence (fate) of emissions from potassium-containing nutrients is measured in kilograms of P to freshwater equivalents.
Marine eutrophication	The environmental persistence (fate) of emissions from nitrogen-containing nutrients is measured in kilograms of N to marine equivalents.
Human toxicity and ecotoxicity	The long-term environmental impact (fate), build-up in the human food chain (exposure), and toxicity (effect) of a chemical are assessed in terms of kilograms of emitted 1,4-dichlorobenzene (1,4-DCB).
Land use	The extent of land altered or utilized over a specific duration is measured in square meters per year (m ² .yr.).
Water use	Quantity of freshwater used, measured in cubic meters of water consumed.
Mineral resource scarcity	The excess ore capacity is measured in kilograms of copper (Cu) equivalents.

Impact Category	Description
Fossil resource scarcity	The fossil fuel potential, determined by the higher heating value, is measured in kilograms of oil equivalents.

Phase 4: Interpretation

The interpretation phase consists of analysing and synthesizing the results obtained from the inventory analysis and impact assessment phases. It includes evaluating the significance of the findings, identifying key drivers of environmental impact, and assessing uncertainties and limitations in the analysis. Based on the results, conclusions and potential pathways to improve environmental performance are established. The interpretation phase aims to provide insights into the environmental performance of the product/system/process under study and guide decision-making towards a more sustainable and resource-efficient product/process/system.

Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA)

MFCA is a powerful tool for cost assessment, going beyond simply tracking monetary transactions. As a tool of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) it systematically monitors and analyses the flow of material, energy, and the associated costs throughout the production process, offering valuable insights for understanding the environmental and financial implications of material and energy usage. By attributing costs to the flows, including wastes and by-products, businesses are empowered to make more sustainable decisions, with transparency in their flows and enabling improvement initiatives.

The MFCA framework revolves around quantity centers, representing pivotal points where the materials' transformation occurs and energy enters the system. By that, these centers connect inputs and outputs throughout the system. Material Balance ensures their equilibrium by meticulously tracking all the flows and ensuring inputs and outputs follow the conservation law. Costs are allocated considering four types: materials, energy, system, and waste management-related costs, facilitating cost calculations. Finally, material flow models depict the entire process, illustrating quantity centers, flow dynamics, and their interactions within the system boundaries [7].

MFCA plays an important role in sustainable decision-making since it identifies critical materials and phases in the production process, facilitating effective solutions that benefit the environment and the production line. Recognising its importance, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) developed ISO 14051 to standardise MFCA methodologies, providing a framework that easily integrates the environmental management standards within the ISO 14000 series [8]. This alignment with broader sustainability evaluations, such as those conducted within the SPINMATE project, underscores MFCA's relevance and suitability for achieving the project's objectives.

In delineating the methodology for MFCA development and reporting, key steps, such as goal scope definition, inventory analysis, quantification, interpretation, and improvements are followed. Table 3 provides a concise overview of each phase of the study, detailing the specific methodologies employed at each stage and incorporating adaptations to ensure alignment with environmental methodologies.

Table 3 – MFCA methodology overview [9].

Phase of the study	Stage of the study	Description
Goal and Scope Definition	Study Objectives	Definition of the study's objectives, significance and purpose
	System Boundaries and Timeframe	Definition of the analysis scope, including boundaries, quantity centers, and time duration
Inventory Analysis	Quantity Centers and Material Flow Mapping (via SUNDIAL)	Map out key material inputs, products, by-products, and waste streams, accompanied by a visual representation of the process, illustrating all quantity centers within the defined system boundaries
	Costs Allocation	Assignment of costs to products or material losses at each quantity center based on the

Phase of the study	Stage of the study	Description
		proportion of material input flowing into products and wastes/by-products
Quantification	Cost Calculations	Quantification of costs and material balance
Interpretation	Data Summary and Interpretation	Compilation of the collected data and results, with its interpretation, providing insights such as trends, patterns, and major findings
Improvements	Improvement Opportunities	Identification of potential reductions in costs, leading to enhanced resource efficiency and improvement of the cost and, consequently, environmental performance

As the inventory is being formed, the data collection, just like the environmental assessment, is done via the Sustainability DDP – SUNDIAL. This tool is crucial for collecting the data in an easy, safe, and organised manner. It facilitates exchanges with partners, compiling all information provided into a single platform and format, allowing easy visualisation of the entire process. The way the information is presented makes it easy to understand the process and facilitates the inputting of the materials, energy, and equipment utilised in the process, including quantities, origin, costs, and transports. This way, the platform optimises one of the most time-consuming stages of the study.

State-of-art analysis

SPINMATE is introducing a new concept to the batteries market. To identify potential environmental and cost concerns and areas for improvement in this technology, it is important to examine existing similar technologies. LIBs are the technologies that SPINMATE aims to surpass. Since these technologies are more mature, understanding their issues, impacts, and risks can provide valuable insights for anticipating potential concerns and challenges with the new technology, even on a small scale.

In this context, LIB will be used as a baseline. Establishing a baseline is important as it provides a benchmark for comparison. This baseline reflects the present state or prevailing conditions, enabling the measurement of changes or enhancements over time. It provides context for understanding the impacts of the product and helps stakeholders identify areas for improvement or optimisation. Additionally, the baseline allows the evaluation of the effectiveness of sustainability initiatives or interventions over time. Without a baseline, it would be challenging to assess the magnitude of changes in performance and determine the success of sustainability efforts. Therefore, establishing a baseline is essential for setting targets, tracking progress, and making informed decisions to promote sustainability and resource efficiency. Figure 3 summarises the approach used to assess the SPINMATE’s results.

Figure 3 - Approach to assess environmental and cost project results.

The battery chemistries to be considered for the baseline were chosen together with the support of all SPINMATE’s partners. For the SPINMATE technology, the SoA baseline selection focused on batteries with similar chemistries (NMCx-graphite) to the SPINMATE chemistry. The electrolyte chosen was “LiPF6 + EC + DMC” because it was the most used and found electrolyte in the literature[10], [11]. Based on this, the following chemistries were selected for the baseline:

- Cathode-Anode: NMC111-Graphite. Electrolyte: LiPF6 + EC + DMC;
- Cathode-Anode: NMC622-Graphite. Electrolyte: LiPF6 + EC + DMC;
- Cathode-Anode: NMC811-Graphite. Electrolyte: LiPF6 + EC + DMC.

The analysis of these chemistries for the baseline aimed to examine challenges, issues, potential environmental impacts, and costs, particularly concerning their production phase, material sourcing, and other related factors.

Environmental SoA

Based on the baseline selection, an extensive literature review of existing environmental life cycle studies on Li-ion batteries was conducted to better understand the key contributors within the battery system. The literature search was conducted using scientific and academic databases, including ScienceDirect, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The search included relevant keywords such as "LCA battery", "LCA Li-Ion battery", "battery environmental impact", "LCA battery production," "LCA Li-ion battery NMC", and "LCA NMC battery". The search focused on publications of NMC811, NMC622, and NMC111 chemistries related to the life cycle assessment of batteries and battery production published between the years 2013 and 2023. The literature analysis gave special attention to the boundaries of the system, the functional unit, the impact methods applied, the main impact contributors, and the challenges. The literature analysed is listed in Table 4.

Table 4 – Literature search of LCA studies on NMC batteries.

Chemistry	FU	Boundary	Impact method	Country (manufacturer)	Data sourcing	Main conclusions
NMC111-S [12]	1 battery pack (43.2 kWh)	Cradle-to-grave	GREET	U.S.	Primary (lab) and secondary (database)	<p>Battery operations are the main source of environmental impact, contributing to over half of the assessed categories.</p> <p>Overall, the LC impacts of this new battery pack (NMC- Silicon Nanowires) are higher than the traditional LIBs (NMCx-C)</p>
NMC – C [13]	Production of one traction battery; 1 kWh	cradle-to-gate	ReCiPe		Primary	The most impact-intensive phase during the production phase was the manufacture of the battery cells, more precisely the positive electrode paste and the negative current collector.
NMC111-C [11]	1 kg of battery pack; 1 kWh capacity	Cradle-to-gate	CML; EcoIndicator; ReCiPe; AADP			<p>NMC presents higher impacts due to the use of Ni and Co.</p> <p>NMCx battery cells with lower consumption of Co present better environmental performance.</p> <p>Substituting Al (Aluminium) for Copper (Cu) in the anode current collector offers the potential to significantly reduce Cu consumption and mitigate the environmental burdens associated with its resource depletion.</p> <p>Reducing or eliminating the use of Co, Ni, and Cu can be viewed as a design goal for developing batteries with low resource demands.</p>
NMC-C [14]	1 kWh capacity	Cradle-to-gate	GREET	China		The production of cathode materials and wrought Al are the main contributors to GHG emissions, collectively accounting for around 75% of the total emissions.
NMC-C [15]	1 kWh;	Cradle-to-gate	GREET	China	Secondary data	In EV batteries, Al, steel and AM are the main drivers of GHG emissions.
NMC-C [16]	250 000 km	Cradle-to-gate	CML2001	China	Primary and secondary	The results show that electricity structure optimization can reduce the life cycle environmental impacts of the EV power system.

Chemistry	FU	Boundary	Impact method	Country	Data sourcing	Main conclusions
NMC111-C [17]	1 pack Li-ion battery (250 kg)	Cradle-to-gate and cradle-to-grave	ReCiPe	RoW - UK	Secondary	Battery cell production is the contributor to the life cycle GHG emissions (cradle-to-gate). Production and processing of Co and Ni have significant impacts on the environment
NMC111-C [18]	1 kWh storage	Cradle-to-gate	REET	U.S.	Primary data	CAM, AI, and energy use for cell production are the main contributors to the environmental impacts of NMC;
NMC622-SiC NMC811-SiC [19]	Production of one traction battery; 1 kWh	Cradle-to-Gate	ReCiPe	China	Secondary	Increasing the Ni content of the cathode can decrease the impacts. Cell manufacturing is the highest contributor to the impact on a battery.
NMC111-C NMC622-C NMC811-C [20]	1 kWh of capacity	Cradle-to-grave	ILCD	-	Primary and secondary data	NMC battery chemistry choices have little impact on overall GHG emissions (GWP). However, using batteries with more Ni increases environmental burdens during production. This downside can be partially balanced by recycling, especially when it recovers more Ni. While battery recycling offers environmental benefits, it cannot fully address the environmental burdens associated with battery production.
NMC-C [21]	25.3 MWh of energy delivered; 1 kWh	Cut-off	CML	Europe	Primary	Battery production and recycling was found to be of minor relevant when the entire life cycle of the batteries was studied.
NMC622-C [22]	1 kWh (energy delivered)	Cradle-to-grave	ILCD	Italy	Primary and secondary	For NMC batteries, production impacts are primarily driven by the cathode active materials (CAM), energy consumption, and battery packaging.

Chemistry	FU	Boundary	Impact method	Country	Data sourcing	Main conclusions
NMC111-C [23]	1 MWh delivered	Cradle-to-grate and Cradle-to-grave	ReCiPe	China	Primary and Secondary	The cathode and anode of the LIB are the components that contribute most significantly to the environmental impacts The EoL of both energy storage systems did not result in substantial impacts, as the metals used in the LIB were assumed to be 95% recycled
MC111-C NMC622-C NMC811-C [24],[25]	1 kWh	Cradle-to-gate; Cradle-to-grave	CML, GREET, ReCiPe ILCD	Europe, Asia, America	Secondary	Cathode production is the main contributor to GHG emissions. The primary reason is the involvement of raw materials like Ni and Co GHG emissions can be effectively reduced through battery material recycling and battery remanufacturing
NMC-C [26]	1 kWh of capacity	Cradle-to-gate	-	Europe, America, Asia	Secondary	The main contributors for the environmental impact of battery manufacturing are associated to cathodes' chemistries; the inclusion of the end-of-life stage can decrease the median value of the observations
NMC111-C NMC622-C NMC811-C [27]	1 kWh of battery capacity	Cradle-to-gate	GREET	America	Secondary	The production of CAMs for the NMC batteries accounted for more than 50% of the batteries' life-cycle GHG emissions The transition to NMC532, NMC622, and NMC 811 from NMC111 led to reductions in impact categories such as GHG emission and Water consumption levels. the NMC811 LIB showed a reduction of 7.5% in GHG emissions compared to the NMC111 LIB.
NMC-C [28]	1 kWh	Cradle-to-grave	ReCiPe	China	Primary and secondary	Large number of carbon emissions during the manufacturing process of cathode materials.

The studies considered relate to LCA studies of battery storage systems for electric mobility and stationery. The studies that considered batteries for EVs focused on comparing EV with combustion engine vehicles and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles [15], [16], [17], [29], and other studies focused on comparing cell chemistries [19], [23], [30]. Most of these studies used primary and secondary data for their research. The LCA studies have been conducted in different geographical regions all over the world, such as Europe, America (predominantly United States, U.S.), and Asia (predominantly China, Japan, and South Korea).

In the literature, different functional units were used to assess the environmental impact of batteries, including per kilometre of travel, per kilowatt-hour of battery storage capacity or delivered, per kilogram of battery, and per battery pack. Figure 4 presents the number of FUs used per publication.

Figure 4 - Number of publications per FU.

Depending on the goal and scope, the reasons to consider these functional units can be:

- Kilometre (km) of travel per battery: This unit evaluates the environmental impact associated with the use phase while operating a vehicle equipped with the battery over a specific distance. This allows a direct comparison with other energy-driven cars in terms of energy consumption and environmental footprint;
- Kilowatt-hour (kWh) of battery storage capacity or delivery: This unit focuses on the environmental impact per unit of energy stored or delivered by the battery itself;
- Kilogram (kg) of battery and battery pack: This unit allows a direct comparison of the environmental impact associated with the entire battery, including materials used in its manufacturing.

It is observed that the most common FU used in the analysis of manufacturing processes is kWh. Since batteries are fundamentally about storing energy, using kWh as the functional unit is well aligned with its core function. It allows researchers to understand the environmental and cost implications of producing a specific amount of energy storage capacity. Since the aim of this document is to study the environmental and cost performance of SSB cells, it was considered that the best functional unit to consider is 1 kWh of battery storage capacity.

Impact methods translate the environmental effects identified in the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) phase into a set of understandable and measurable impact categories. The literature review reveals that the most used impact methods for assessing Li-ion batteries are GREET, CML, ReCiPe, and ILCD, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Number of publications per impact method.

As observed in Figure 5, ReCiPe impact method was the most used impact method for assessing the environmental impacts of Li-ion battery systems, followed by GREET. GREET was developed by Argonne National Laboratory, a research center of the U.S. Department of Energy, to evaluate the energy and environmental impacts of transportation fuels and technologies in the U.S. While GREET has been adapted for use in other countries like China, the core model is based on data sources and assumptions specific to the U.S. [31]. The ReCiPe impact method offers a wide range of impact categories with different levels of detail (18 impact categories), covering both midpoint and endpoint indicators; besides this, it's widely accepted by the scientific community[6]. ReCiPe is the most commonly used and comprehensive impact assessment method in the literature, it was therefore chosen for this study.

It's predominant that Europe has the lowest GHG emissions from battery manufacturing compared to America and Asia [21], [23]. Table 5 demonstrates the ranges of these regions.

Table 5 - CO₂eq/kWh emissions of battery manufacturing (per cradle-to-gate) [15], [16], [22], [24].

	America	Asia	Europe
Carbon footprint range (kg CO₂ eq./kWh)	73-56	60-168	56-51

It was consistently identified in the literature that the production phase was the main impact contributor to a battery life cycle. This is mainly associated with the cell production, specifically the cathode processing. The ones responsible for the high impact of the cathode were its AM (NMC), more precisely, the Nickel (Ni) and Cobalt (Co). Additionally, electricity is the second main contributor, but this contribution is influenced by the manufacturer country [11], [15], [17], [22], [23], [27], [32].

The studies that included end-of-life by recycling and those that incorporated recycled materials in the manufacturing phase obtained a lower environmental footprint, as demonstrated in the Da Silva study [23]. The use of renewable energy also supports the reduction of impacts and the country's electricity mix [21].

Relevant LCA studies were analysed for the specified chemistries. Table 6 presents the carbon footprint ranges for each chemistry (kg of CO₂ equivalent per kWh).

Table 6 - GHG emissions (KgCO₂-eq/kWh) of the production of LIBs [25], [33].

	NMC111	NMC622	NMC811
Carbon footprint range (kg CO₂ eq./kWh)	56 – 130.4	54-160	53-140

The carbon footprints exhibit minimal variation between the chemistries. NMC111 has the highest values, although it has the narrowest range between the lowest and highest values. NMC622 demonstrates slightly lower impact values than NMC111 and has the widest range among the three chemistries, while NMC811 has the lowest impact.

Additionally, studies that didn't specify the NMC composition (NMC_x) reported a range from 53 to 534 kg CO₂ eq./kWh. It's important to emphasise that these variations are significantly influenced by the country's electricity mix and the selected impact category method.

While conducting an LCA study, it is relevant to mention that considering the carbon footprint is important, but it's not enough to understand the overall environmental impact. Other environmental indicators, such as water consumption, ecotoxicity, biodiversity impact, and others, are equally important to gain a comprehensive understanding of the product's overall environmental impact.

Subsequently, to analyse the potential environmental impacts and benefits of the SPINMATE cell and pilot line with the available EV battery technology, a baseline with specific reference conditions from the SoA was defined. This baseline will later be correlated with SPINMATE's technology. This framework was developed to create traceability of all of the process flows within the cradle-to-gate scope and to establish a correlation with SPINMATE's LCA model.

In this context, key information was defined as the goal and scope, functional unit, and system boundaries, as demonstrated in Table 7, aiming to provide a better perspective of the identified impacts and gaps in the current literature data, as well as the main hotspots of environmental impacts during the production phase of currently available chemistries.

Table 7 - LCA methodology for the baseline.

Goal and scope	Quantify the environmental performance of battery-pack system: NMC111, NMC622 and NMC811
Functional Unit	1 kWh of capacity
Boundaries	Cradle-to-gate
Software	SimaPro v9.5 [34]
Database	Ecoinvent v3.9.1. [34]
Impact method	ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) v1.08 [6]
Geography	China

China is the world's largest manufacturer of Li-ion batteries, as shown in Figure 6. This dominance in the Li-ion battery market emphasises China's pivotal role in global battery production and establishes it as a relevant reference for evaluating industry standards. Consequently, for this baseline, China has been selected as a relevant competitor to consider for comparison and correlation of SPINMATE's technology performance.

Figure 6 - Share of the global Li-ion battery manufacturing capacity in 2021 [3].

The inventories used as references for the modelling were:

- NMC111, NMC622 and NMC811: Ecoinvent v3.9.1 life cycle database [18].

The chosen inventories were modelled in the Simapro V9.5.0.0[34] software, and the impacts were quantified with the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) v1.08 [6].

The results derived from this evaluation allow for more current SoA results of these chemistries for later correlation with SPINMATE's technology.

These chemistries were modelled, at battery pack level, in all of the 18 impact categories of the ReCiPe method per 1 kWh of battery capacity (functional unit), considering the life cycle phases of: extraction, transport, processing and production. These impact categories are:

1. Global warming (kg CO₂ eq.);
2. Stratospheric ozone depletion (kg CFC11 eq.);
3. Ionizing radiation (kg Bq Co-60 eq.);
4. Ozone formation, human health (NO_x eq.);
5. Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq.);
6. Ozone formation (kg NO_x eq.);
7. Terrestrial acidification (kg SO₂ eq.);
8. Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq.);
9. Marine eutrophication (kg N eq.);
10. Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DCB);
11. Freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DCB);
12. Marine ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DCB);
13. Human carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1,4-DCB);
14. Human non-carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1,4-DCB);
15. Land use (m²a crop eq.);
16. Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu eq.);
17. Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq.);
18. Water consumption (m³).

The impacts of each NMC_x battery-pack are discriminated by battery cell, BMS, Packaging, electronic components, electricity, polymers and precious metals. The results are expressed in "ecopoints" (pt). The ecopoint unit aggregates and normalises the environmental impacts of a product or process into a single score. This score facilitates the comparison and evaluation of different products or processes based on their overall environmental impact. In the annexes, the

graphical results are also presented in ReCiPe Midpoint (H) v1.08, and the numerical results are presented in tables either ReCiPe Endpoint (H) v1.08 and Midpoint (H) v1.08.

For all of the analysed chemistries, the findings indicate that the battery cell consistently had the most significant impact among all the observed battery pack components (BMS, Packaging, electronic components, electricity, polymers and precious metals), as demonstrated in Figure 7, Figure 9 and Figure 11 for the NMC111, NMC622 and NMC811 chemistries, respectively. A further analysis of the cell indicates that these impacts are mainly attributed to cathode production, which is related to the consumption of materials such as Nickel and Cobalt, as presented in Figure 8 (NMC111), Figure 10 (NMC622) and Figure 12 (NMC811). These results are also aligned with the main conclusions from the current literature.

NMC111

The baseline results for the NMC 111 chemistry are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack in Pt.

In all impact categories, battery cells are the main contributors, with contributions between 61% and 99%. Following the battery cells, the second main impact contributor is precious metals, with contributions between 0.52% and 17%.

At the battery cell level, it's observed in Figure 8 that the main responsible for the impacts is the cathode, being the main impact contributor in 13 impact categories (Global warming, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ionizing radiation, ozone formation, fine particular matter formation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity, Land use, Mineral resource scarcity, Fossil resource scarcity and Water consumption), with contributions ranging around 31-97%. This is highly associated with the consumption of materials such as Ni and Co. The second main impact contributor is copper. Copper is the main impact contributor in four impact categories (Terrestrial ecotoxicity, Marine ecotoxicity, Human carcinogenic toxicity and Human non-carcinogenic toxicity), with contributions of around 43-59%. This is mostly related to the copper used in the copper collector foil. The results are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery cell in Pt.

NMC622

The baseline results for the NMC622 chemistry are presented in Figure 9.

In all impact categories, battery cells are the main contributors, contributing between 61% and 99%. Following the battery cells, the second main contributor is precious metals, contributing between 1% and 17%.

Figure 9 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack in Pt.

At the battery cell level, it's observed in Figure 10 that the main impact contributor is the cathode, being the main impact contributor in 13 impact categories (Global warming, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ionizing radiation, Ozone formation, Fine particular matter formation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Freshwater ecotoxicity, Land use, Mineral resource scarcity, Fossil resource scarcity and Water consumption), with contributions ranging from 44-97%. This is highly associated with the consumption of materials such as Ni and Co. The second main impact contributor is copper. Copper is the main impact contributor in four impact categories (Terrestrial ecotoxicity, Marine ecotoxicity, Human carcinogenic toxicity and Human non-carcinogenic toxicity), with contributions around 44-60%. This is mostly related to the copper used in the copper collector foil. In Figure 10 are depicted the results.

Figure 10 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery cell in Pt.

NMC811

The baseline results for the NMC811 chemistry are presented in Figure 11.

It's observed that the main impact contributor is the battery cells in all impact categories, with contributions between 57-98%. Following the battery cells, the second main impact contributor is the precious metals, with contributions between 1-19%.

Figure 11 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack in Pt.

At the battery cell level, as illustrated in Figure 12, the cathode is identified as the primary impact contributor, dominating 13 impact categories (Global warming, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ionizing radiation, ozone formation, Fine particular matter formation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Freshwater ecotoxicity, Land use, Mineral resource scarcity, Fossil resource scarcity and Water consumption), with contributions ranging around 34-95%. This significant impact is closely linked to the consumption of materials such as nickel (Ni) and cobalt (Co). Copper emerges as the second main contributor, affecting five impact categories (Terrestrial ecotoxicity, Marine ecotoxicity, Human carcinogenic toxicity, Human non-carcinogenic toxicity and Land use), with contributions around 37-63%. This impact is mainly associated with the copper used in the copper collector foil. The results are further detailed in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery cell in Pt.

Costs SoA

In the context of cost assessment, the literature review of existing studies on Li-ion batteries was conducted using academic and scientific databases such as Google Scholar and Research Gate. The keywords searched were “battery”, “lithium-ion”, “battery costs”, “manufacturing”, “economic assessment”, “cost assessment”, “cost breakdown” and “bill of material”. Table 8 summarises the articles selected according to the criteria of having data on NMC chemistries as the CAM, review and compilation of studies about costs of batteries, cost data for each battery component, and data on production procedures and related expenses, published between 2014 and 2024.

Table 8 - Literature search of cost studies on Lithium batteries.

Chemistry	Boundary	Method	Main objective	Main conclusions
Various [35]	Materials and manufacturing of batteries, cathodes, and anodes.	Review of literature on articles incorporating various methods and techniques.	Review the methods and results of battery cost forecasting, identify key trends in this area, and ensure transparency regarding the methodological and technological details	The cost of battery cells varies from 64 to 439 \$ per kWh, depending on chemistry and scale of production. For pack-level, NMC chemistries show costs of 84 \$/kWh to 432 \$/kWh. Different methods can be employed for cost estimation, such as technological learning, literature-based projections, expert elicitation, and bottom-up modelling. The analysis reveals a strong belief in declining future battery costs.
Various [36]	CAM synthesis, electrode production, cell production, cell conditioning, and end-of-life treatment (recycling)	Bottom-up cost estimation technique	Assess the costs, carbon footprint, and environmental impacts of lithium-ion batteries	Battery cell manufacturing costs \$94.5 per kWh, with an additional \$6.8 to \$8.6 per kWh for end-of-life recycling. Materials account for 69% of the total cell costs, with CAM synthesis being a significant contributor. Hydrometallurgical recycling costs are relatively low compared to cell manufacturing and have minimal impact on overall environmental impacts. The benefits of recycling, particularly for critical raw materials (CRM), outweigh the burdens associated with it.
Various [37]	Materials and manufacturing of cell chemistries for anodes and cathodes.	A bottom-up approach based on other cost models.	Develop a material cost model for evaluating cell chemistry alternatives for li-ion battery anodes and cathodes in electric vehicle applications.	Material costs, particularly for LIBs, are a significant cost driver due to the high demand for cobalt, nickel, and lithium. The cathode emerges as the primary contributor to costs across various chemistries, including LFP, LMO, and NMC. The "BatPaC" model is identified as the most suitable among cost models, although it is noted for its high calculation complexity. Additionally, using AMs with high specific energy can help reduce material costs and enhance cell performance.
Various [38]	Materials and manufacturing of LIBs pack technologies in industrial production.	A bottom-up approach based on "real-world" material costs.	Develop a method for calculating electric vehicle lithium-ion battery pack performance and cost,	Raw material price fluctuations, particularly in cobalt, significantly impact CAM manufacturing costs and the overall expense of lithium-ion batteries. Approximately 60 to 80% of CAM costs are dictated by raw material prices. Cathode accounts for the majority of cell costs, with LFP and NMC 111 emerging as the costliest chemistries. Technologies with higher nickel content and

Chemistry	Boundary	Method	Main objective	Main conclusions
				reduced cobalt dependence, like NMC-811 and NCA, offer potential for cost reduction and enhanced performance.
Various [39]	Materials and manufacturing of battery cells with different CAM chemistries.	Literature search and review.	Provide a systematic overview of scientific publications related to battery cost modelling and evaluate the benefits, reliability, and transparency of these models.	In SoA LIB cells, cathode materials represent 48-52% of total material costs, followed by anode materials at 13-15%, separator at 13%, and electrolyte at 9-10%. Material costs typically constitute 60-80% of total costs, with manufacturing costs making up the remainder. The BatPaC model is widely utilized and recognized as one of the most impactful models in the research community, often serving as a primary data source. Quantitative techniques like parametric and analytical methods are commonly employed for cost estimation. Research indicates a strong correlation between total battery costs and material costs.

Key findings indicate that material costs, particularly for CAMs, are a significant cost driver due to the high demand and prices of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) like **Co, Ni, and Li**. The study of Duffner et al. found that 60-80% of costs are based on materials, making price fluctuations a major factor in cell manufacturing costs and the overall cost of LIBs [39]. They also find that cathode materials account for 48–52% of total material costs, followed by anode materials at 13–15% [36].

Gutsch & Leker support this by stating that materials represent about 69% of total cell costs, with CAMs being the largest contributor[36]. They estimate the total battery cell manufacturing costs at \$94.5 per kWh. Mauler et al. (2021) show that cell costs can vary widely, from \$64 to \$439 per kWh, due to differences in chemistry, production scale, and techniques. NMC chemistry costs at the pack level range from \$84 to \$432 per kWh [35].

Technologies with higher nickel content and lower cobalt dependency, such as NMC811 and NCA, show potential for cost reduction and improved performance. Duffner et al. identify that parametric and analytical methods are commonly used for cost estimation [39]. Despite the complexity, the BatPaC model is considered the most suitable and effective for cost estimation by the research community, as noted by Petri et al., Wentker et al., and Duffner et al. [37], [38], [39].

Subsequently, to analyse the cost dynamics within battery manufacturing and to compare the cost of SPINMATE cells and pilot lines with existing EV battery technologies, INEGI also defined a baseline for comparison and correlation with SPINMATE’s technology. Key information is presented in Table 9.

Table 9 - Costs methodology for the baseline.

Goal and scope	Quantify the costs of the battery-pack system: NMC111, NMC622, and NMC811
Functional Unit	1 kWh of capacity
Boundaries	Cradle-to-gate
Database	BatPaC 5.1 Database
Analysis type	Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA)

The reference inventories were sourced from the BatPaC Database and modified to fit the MFCA format. Quantifications were performed using Excel, focusing on material and energy costs within the production process. This evaluation provides up-to-date results of the SoA of these chemistries, allowing for correlation with SPINMATE’s technology.

This way, applying the MFCA framework requires prioritising the analysis of material and energy flows throughout production to understand associated cost flows. Consequently, a Bill of Materials (BOM) was initially prepared using the BatPaC Database as a reference, supplemented by insights from the project partners. Assumptions for cell, module, and pack designs were established as follows:

- 240 cells per pack;
- 12 cells per module;
- 20 modules per pack;
- 100kWh as the total target battery system energy;
- 20 cell interconnects per module (including those needed for tabs to terminals);
- 4 cells in parallel per module;
- 4 rows of modules per pack;
- 5 modules in a row per pack;

- 24 module interconnects per pack.

After the establishment of the BOM, the cost inventory of the project baseline was developed by including in the BOM the quantities of each material, the energy used in the processing and assembly, the associated purchase costs of the materials, and the cost of energy usage for each of the three chemistries analysed in the baseline (NMC111, NMC622, and NMC811). It is important to note that in these cost inventories, costs related to equipment, taxes, fees, permits, fines, internal personnel, equipment depreciation, and external expenses were intentionally excluded, this way the assessment focused solely on the material and energy usage and their dynamics throughout the production process. Other than that, costs associated with material transport, as well as the purchase, installation, and maintenance of machinery and equipment used in the process, were also not included. Figure 13 provides a summary of the strategy for the construction of the cost baseline.

Figure 13 - Scheme of the strategy for the cost baseline.

In addressing waste considerations, BatPaC has a notable deficiency in clearly documenting the waste from the manufacturing process. Instead of offering a detailed overview of waste generation throughout the whole process, it only presents clear values regarding recoverable materials rejected from the plant floor of cell-level components, including both materials in cells rejected after testing and other materials available for recycling (scrap materials from electrode slitting, coating, etc.). As this is the only point of reference in the database for waste generated by the manufacturing process, it's the only data used in that regard, restricting this specific analysis exclusively to the cell level. Percentages derived from the quantities provided by BatPaC for each of the chemistries analysed are summarized in Table 10.

Table 10 – Percentage of wastes considered per cell component indicated in BatPaC Database.

Component	% (m/m)		
	NMC 111	NMC 622	NMC 811
Positive active material	10.4 %	10.4 %	10.4 %
Negative active material	10.4 %	10.4%	10.4 %
Positive current collector	15.9 %	18.9 %	15.9 %
Negative current collector	15.9 %	18.9 %	15.9 %
Positive terminal	4.7 %	4.7 %	4.7 %
Negative terminal	3.1 %	2.8 %	2.5 %
Separator	5.7 %	6.1 %	5.7 %
Electrolyte	5.7 %	6.1 %	5.7 %
Cell container	4.7 %	4.8 %	4.8 %

Based on the outlined assumptions, results were obtained for the baseline of the three chemistries considered and are shown in the following sub-sections. The BatPaC database, with detailed information on components, quantities, and costs up to the cell-level, enables a comprehensive analysis. By studying the levels separately and examining the components integrated at each stage, it's possible to identify specific cost drivers for optimisation and understand the causes of their contribution to the total costs. This detailed analysis can also highlight where cost reductions can have the most significant impact.

Therefore, the cost baseline results are presented at three different levels: cell, module, and pack. Additionally, the Bill of Materials (BOM) can be observed in this context.

NMC 111

The baseline results for the NMC 111 chemistry are presented in Table 11 for cell-level, Table 12 for module-level, and Table 13 for pack-level. At cell-level materials, the active material of the cathode is the major contributor to the costs, followed by the active material of the anode. This high contribution can be explained by the large quantities used compared to other inputs, along with the high prices associated with the elements that integrate these materials: the CRMs. Chemicals such as cobalt sulphate, nickel sulphate, and manganese sulphate, present in the active materials, integrate the CRMs that, due to their economic significance and supply risk, are categorised as such [40].

Consequently, they tend to have high demand and prices, justifying their significant cost contributions. Moreover, there are different levels of criticality within the critical materials, both because of demand and scarcity. In the case of the NMC, cobalt is the material with the highest associated cost, justified by both supply risk and economic importance.

Regarding materials at the module-level, the Module Management System (MMS) stands out as the biggest contributor to module costs, representing 61% of the total. According to the BatPaC manual [41], this component includes multiple parts that add up to its cost, such as fuses, temperature sensors, and sense PCBs, adding to also equipment for interfacing the cells and connectors from the inside to the outside of the module. This complexity and quantity of different specialised parts make up for a relatively high cost of the MMS.

At the pack level, the Battery Management System (BMS) plays a major role in pack costs, accounting for 55%. Similar to the MMS, the BMS is expensive because of its complexity, number of different components, and high associated prices compared with other components introduced at pack-level, which justifies its significant impact on total costs.

Table 11 - MFCA inputs at cell-level for NMC 111 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Positive Electrode (cathode)		
Active material (NMC111)	730.61 g	20.59 €/cell
Conductive additive	13.79 g	0.09 €/cell
Binder	13.79 g	0.19 €/cell
Binder solvent	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Negative Electrode (anode)		
Active material (Graphite)	393.2 g	3.27 €/cell
Conductive additive	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Binder	7.27 g	0.07 €/cell
Binder solvent	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Other Cell Materials		
Positive current collector	44.69 g	0.20 €/cell
Negative current collector	104.27 g	1.29 €/cell
Separators	13.63 g	1.60 €/cell
Electrolyte	166.57 g	1.15 €/cell
Positive terminal (Al)	8.07 g	0.02 €/cell
Negative terminal (Cu)	17.58 g	0.14 €/cell
Cell container (PET-AI-PP)	27.79 g	0.08 €/cell

Component	Quantity	Cost
Energy at \$0,04/kWh	13.92 kWh	0.51 €/cell
Total		29.21 €/cell

Table 12 - MFCA inputs at module-level for NMC 111 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Cost of battery module purchased items (excluding cell materials)		
Al thermal conductors	525.80 g	2.83 €/module
Module management system (MMS)	N/A	18.20 €/module
Cell interconnects (Cu)	288.48 g	3.06 €/module
Interconnect panel, PP	167.54 g	0.73 €/module
Module terminals	163.02 g	1.63 €/module
Module enclosures	675.17 g	2.88 €/module
Provision for gas release	5.00 g	0.46 €/module
Energy at 0,04\$/kWh	7.48 kWh	0.28 €/module
Total		30.08 €/module

Table 13 – MFCA inputs at pack-level for NMC 111 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Cost of battery pack purchased items (excluding cell and module materials)		
Row rack materials (not including cooling panels materials)	38.35 kg	50.65 €/pack
Elastomer pads between modules	0.25 g	2.96 €/pack
Module Interconnects	0.15 kg	38.55 €/pack
Bus bar for battery packs	2.02 kg	16.76 €/pack
Cooling panels, S.S.	13.74 kg	39.24 €/pack
Coolant manifolds	1.16 kg	9.51 €/pack
Pack terminals and seals	0.85 kg	7.69 €/pack
Pack support frame	13.35 kg	17.27 €/pack
Pack jacket (top & interior base)	26.80 kg	81.02 €/pack
Pack jacket (exterior base)	15.21 kg	22.10 €/pack
Pack jacket insulation	1.44 g	12.47 €/pack
Baseline thermal system	3.00 kg	73.93 €/pack
Heating system	N/A	18.48 €/pack
Energy at 0,04\$/kWh	150.25 kWh	5.55 €/pack
Total		396.19 €/pack
Total Cost of Battery Management System (BMS)	3.46 kg	482,85 €/pack
Total		879.04 €/pack

NMC 622

For the NMC 622 chemistry, the baseline results are presented in Table 14 at cell-level, Table 15 for module-level, and Table 16 at pack-level. Similar to what was observed for the NMC 111 chemistry, the main cost contributors are consistent for NMC 622.

That said, the main contributors to cell-level materials are the active materials of the cathode (~68%) and the anode (~12%), respectively. The MMS is the main contributor to module-level materials, accounting for more than 60% of the module cost. Finally, the BMS is the main contributor to pack-level materials, accounting for 55% of the pack costs.

Even though the materials integrated into the system are the same, their quantities are different, leading to variations in each input's contribution when, for example, compared to NMC111. These differences are particularly significant for the cost of the CAMs, where the proportions of CRM, such as Co and Ni, significantly influence the total costs.

Table 14 - MFCA inputs at cell-level for NMC 622 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Positive Electrode (cathode)		
Active material (NMC622)	657.87 g	18.54 €/cell
Conductive additive	12.42 g	0.08 €/cell
Binder	12.42 g	0.17 €/cell
Binder solvent	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Negative Electrode (anode)		
Active material (Graphite)	395.00 g	3.29 €/cell
Conductive additive	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Binder	7.30 g	0.07 €/cell
Binder solvent	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Other Cell Materials		
Positive current collector	41.50 g	0.23 €/cell
Negative current collector	96.99 g	1.43 €/cell
Separators	12.33 g	1.54 €/cell
Electrolyte	158.43 g	1.17 €/cell
Positive terminal (Al)	7.97 g	0.02 €/cell
Negative terminal (Cu)	17.31 g	0.14 €/cell
Cell container (PET-AI-PP)	26.36 g	0.07 €/cell
Energy at \$0.04/kWh	13.52 kWh	0.50 €/cell
Total		27.24 €/cell

Table 15 - MFCA inputs at module-level for NMC 622 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Cost of battery module purchased items (excluding cell materials)		
Al thermal conductors	496.96 g	2.77 €/module
Module management system (MMS)	N/A	18.20 €/module
Cell interconnects (Cu)	292.20 g	3.09 €/module
Interconnect panel. PP	164.92 g	0.72 €/module
Module terminals	163.37 g	1.64 €/module
Module enclosures	661.59 g	2.85 €/module
Provision for gas release	5.00 g	0.46 €/module
Energy at 0.04\$/kWh	7.48 kWh	0.28 €/module
Total		30.01 €/module

Table 16 - MFCA inputs at pack-level for NMC 622 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Cost of battery pack purchased items (excluding cell and module materials)		
Row rack materials (not including cooling panels materials)	37.72 kg	49.89 €/pack
Elastomer pads between modules	0.24 g	2.96 €/pack
Module Interconnects	0.15 kg	38.61 €/pack
Bus bar for battery packs	1.97 kg	16.39 €/pack
Cooling panels. S.S.	13.51 kg	38.64 €/pack
Coolant manifolds	1.14 kg	9.31 €/pack
Pack terminals and seals	0.86 kg	7.71 €/pack
Pack support frame	13.30 kg	17.21 €/pack
Pack jacket (top & interior base)	26.50 kg	80.15 €/pack
Pack jacket (exterior base)	15.12 kg	21.99 €/pack
Pack jacket insulation	1.43 g	12.35 €/pack
Baseline thermal system	3.00 kg	73.93 €/pack
Heating system	N/A	18.48 €/pack
Energy at 0.04\$/kWh	150.25 kWh	5.55 €/pack
Total		393.17 €/pack
Total Cost of Battery Management System (BMS)	3.46 kg	483.47 €/pack
Total		876.64 €/pack

NMC 811

For the NMC 811 chemistry, the baseline results are presented in Table 17 at cell-level, Table 18 at module-level, and Table 19 at pack-level. This chemistry is also consistent with the other chemistries analysed. As previously mentioned, the NMC811 BOM, aside from the cathode's active material, comprises the same inputs, although in slightly different quantities.

The active materials of the cathode (~72%) and the anode (~11%) are the main contributors to the cell-level costs, respectively. At module-level materials, the MMS is the main contributor, accounting for about 62% of the module costs. At pack-level, the BMS is the main contributor to the pack costs, accounting for 57% of the pack costs.

Table 17 - MFCA inputs at cell-level for NMC 811 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Positive Electrode (cathode)		
Active material (NMC811)	589.79 g	18.80 €/cell
Conductive additive	11.13 g	0.07 €/cell
Binder	11.13 g	0.15 €/cell
Binder solvent	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Negative Electrode (anode)		
Active material (Graphite+Si 5%)	305.66 g	2.98 €/cell
Conductive additive	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Binder	5.65 g	0.05 €/cell
Binder solvent	N/A	0.00 €/cell
Other Cell Materials		
Positive current collector	36.48 g	0.17 €/cell
Negative current collector	85.31 g	1.06 €/cell
Separators	11.05 g	1.30 €/cell
Electrolyte	132.25 g	0.92 €/cell
Positive terminal (Al)	6.98 g	0.02 €/cell
Negative terminal (Cu)	15.12 g	0.12 €/cell
Cell container (PET-Al-PP)	23.08 g	0.06 €/cell
Energy at \$0.04/kWh	12.96 kWh	0.48 €/cell
Total		26.18 €/cell

Table 18 – MFCA inputs at module-level for NMC 811 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Cost of battery module purchased items (excluding cell materials)		
Al thermal conductors	432.95 g	2.62 €/module
Module management system (MMS)	N/A	18.20 €/module
Cell interconnects (Cu)	232.13 g	2.61 €/module
Interconnect panel. PP	150.61 g	0.69 €/module
Module terminals	179.61 g	1.69 €/module
Module enclosures	602.84 g	2.72 €/module
Provision for gas release	5.00 g	0.46 €/module
Energy at 0.04\$/kWh	7.48 kWh	0.28 €/module
Total		29.28 €/module

Table 19 - MFCA inputs at pack-level for NMC 811 for the cost baseline.

Component	Quantity	Cost
Cost of battery pack purchased items (excluding cell and module materials)		
Row rack materials (not including cooling panels materials)	34.68 kg	46.16 €/pack
Elastomer pads between modules	0.20 g	2.96 €/pack
Module Interconnects	0.16 kg	39.93 €/pack
Bus bar for battery packs	1.94 kg	16.09 €/pack
Cooling panels. S.S.	12.34 kg	35.62 €/pack
Coolant manifolds	1.07 kg	8.86 €/pack
Pack terminals and seals	0.89 kg	7.99 €/pack
Pack support frame	12.82 kg	16.62 €/pack
Pack jacket (top & interior base)	24.54 kg	74.45 €/pack
Pack jacket (exterior base)	14.08 kg	20.66 €/pack
Pack jacket insulation	1.32 g	11.44 €/pack
Baseline thermal system	3.00 kg	73.93 €/pack
Heating system	N/A	18.48 €/pack
Energy at 0.04\$/kWh	150.25 kWh	5.55 €/pack
Total		378.75 €/pack
Total Cost of Battery Management System (BMS)	3.46 kg	496.19 €/pack
Total		874.94 €/pack

Comparison of the baseline results

Table 20 outlines the compilation of inputs for all three chemistries, considering one pack per chemistry.

Table 20 - Overview of the cost baseline results at pack-level for the FU of 100kWh.

Component	NMC 111		NMC 622		NMC 811	
	Cost	%	Cost	%	Cost	%
Cells	7009.41 €	82.6 %	6536.86 €	81.6 %	6282.01 €	81.1 %
Modules (excluding cells)	601.59 €	7.1 %	600.26 €	7.5 %	585.63 €	7.6 %
Pack (excluding cells and modules)	879.04 €	10.4 %	876.64 €	10.9 %	874.94 €	11.3 %
Total	8490.05 €	-	8013.76 €	-	7742.57 €	-
Part of the total going to wastes	609.73 €	7.2 %	594.53 €	7.4 %	561.64 €	7.3 %

To ensure alignment with the function unit of the project (1 kWh), the results had to be adjusted. Based on the assumptions and default values from the database, where the total battery pack energy is set at 100 kWh, a conversion of the data was performed. The adjusted values are presented in Table 21 and Figure 14.

Table 21 – Overview of the cost baseline results for the FU of 1 kWh.

Component	NMC 111		NMC 622		NMC 811	
	Cost	%	Cost	%	Cost	%
Cells	70.09 €	82.6 %	65.37 €	81.6 %	62.82 €	81.1 %
Modules (excluding cells)	6.02 €	7.1 %	6.00 €	7.5 %	5.86 €	7.6 %
Pack (excluding cells and modules)	8.79 €	10.4 %	8.77 €	10.9 %	8.75 €	11.3 %
Total	84.90 €	-	80.14 €	-	77.43 €	-
Part of the total going to wastes	6.10 €	7.2 %	5.95 €	7.4 %	5.62 €	7.3 %

Figure 14 - Distribution of total costs for NMC 111, NMC 622, and NMC 811.

The results reveal that for all three chemistries analysed, the cost associated with the production of the cells is the main contributor to the total cost, accounting for roughly 80% of the total cost. As already mentioned, among the cell components, the positive electrode AM—NMC 111, NMC

622, and NMC 811—contributes the most to the costs. The comparison between chemistries reveals that the costliest cell is the one with NMC 111, followed by NMC 622 and NMC 811.

The positive electrode AM composition has “Critical Materials” chemicals. As mentioned above, these tend to be in high demand and high price, which explains their significant cost contribution. Cobalt is the material with the highest associated cost. its proportion influences the final cost: NMC 111 is the most expensive cell because it has the highest quantity, and NMC 811 is the cheapest because it has the lowest amount.

Packaging materials and purchased items are the second largest contributor to the total costs, accounting for 10.4 % of NMC 111, 10.9 % for NMC 622, and 11.4 % for NMC 811. As already mentioned, the BMS stands out as the main contributor at pack-level. This is attributed to the high technological complexity, high cost of its production, and, consequently, its purchase compared to other components introduced at pack-level [42]. When comparing the chemistries, the differences in pack costs are not as notably pronounced, mainly due to the small size variations in some of the components, such as the differences in the pack jacket parts.

Energy consumption costs represent only about 1.6 % of the total costs for all three chemistries, with over 90 % associated with the cell production phase. In terms of waste, the percentage of the total materials used at cell-level that accounted for by rejected materials is 7.2% for NMC 111, 7.4% for NMC 622, and 7.3% for NMC 811. The material with the largest mass rejected across all chemistries is positive active material. As positive active material is also the largest contributor to the total costs, focusing on initiatives aimed at the responsible use of critical materials seems to be an interesting path for resource and financial optimisation.

SPINMATE small-scale cell components development processes

This section describes the characteristics of SPINMATE's technology for the SSB small-scale cell prototypes. Note that at this phase, this technology was still in the developmental stage, and the information provided was based on its current state. This information was collected between M17 and M22.

The processes analysed were from WP3 activities, which consisted of developing and optimising different components and formulations within the cell.

These analyses follow the pilot activities conducted in each task as follows:

- T3.1: Raw material optimisation and supply:
 - ST3.1.1: Advanced CAM: NMC powder fabrication;
 - ST 3.1.2: Li metal foil anode with protection layer and upscaling: Lithium-Metal production;
 - ST 3.1.3: Solid polymer electrolyte: Electrolyte production.

- T3.2: Processing definition of cathode and electrolyte layers:
 - ST 3.2.1: Optimization and development of positive electrode: Cathode dry and cathode wet processing.

To safeguard confidentiality, specific material names have been omitted from this document since it is public.

NMC powder production

This process consisted of the fabrication and optimisation of the AM, NMC811, based powder in order to identify the best formulation for cathode formulation. This process consisted of the following steps (Figure 15):

Solution production

This process begins with the preparation of four water-based solutions for each material: lithium (Li), nickel (Ni), manganese (Mn), and cobalt (Co).

The elements are received as salts of each element, which are soluble in water. Each precursor solution is standardised, and the concentration of each element is determined. Now, these solutions are ready to be mixed.

Mixing

These four solutions containing each element are combined in proportions to achieve the desired composition in the final powder. In the case of volatile elements, such as Li, some excess of that element might be added.

Spray pyrolysis

The solution is then atomised into a furnace at high temperatures, causing water evaporation, the burning off of organic additives, and salt decomposition into oxides. From this step, a raw powder is obtained and is collected for subsequent post-treatment.

Calcination I

The raw powder is subjected to a certain temperature within a furnace. The purpose of this process is to remove residual organics and other raw materials that may produce corrosive fumes in the O₂ furnace for the second annealing. For calcination in air this step is usually not necessary.

Calcination II/Annealing

The mixed oxide powder is gradually heated to a specific temperature in O₂ or air to achieve phase purity and acceptable levels of Ni/Li cation mixing.

Milling (optional)

The powder is dry ball milled between the first and second calcination or before sieving.

Sieve

To break or remove any large agglomerates.

Figure 15 - Process flow of the NMC811 fabrication process.

Lithium-Metal anode production

This process consists of the production of the Lithium metal anode. The entire process of lithium anode production is done by a continuous roll-to-roll production process where the unrolled section of copper foil substrate is under tension. The production process consists of two steps (Figure 16):

Lithium deposition

The copper foil substrate is unrolled and undergoes lithium deposition. The stretched copper is exposed to lithium vapour, and the lithium is deposited on the copper foil.

Protective layer deposition

Then, the coated copper undergoes a magnetron sputtering process, where the protective layer is sputtered on the lithium surface. This coated foil is rolled on an empty core along with interleaf material (BOPP film), which is supplied from a roll that unrolls at a given angular speed.

The purpose of the BOPP film is to maintain the quality of the coated foil during storage and transport.

Figure 16 - Process flow of the Li-M anode.

Cathode wet processing

This process consists of the production of the solid-state positive electrode and consists of the following steps (Figure 17):

Mixing

This step consists of the mixing of the active and inactive materials.

First, a solution of polymer (5% in NMP) was prepared, and the corresponding amount was weighted in a beaker. Then, carbon black (C45) was slowly added (and more NMP), and the corresponding solution was mechanically stirred overnight, and solution A was obtained.

Afterwards, Li salt was dissolved separately in NMP by magnetic stirring, and a solution B was obtained.

In parallel, the required amount of ionic liquid was added to solution A and kept mechanically stirred, obtaining solution C.

Subsequently, solution C and solution B were mixed by mechanical stirring.

Finally, NMC811 was slowly added, and the final solution was mechanically stirred. A slurry is obtained.

Coating

This slurry is coated in the base coater. The active layer of the current collector is coated over the current collector (Al/C).

Drying

In the same basecoater, the ovens dry the active layer and evaporate the NMP solvent. The final output is a roll of dry cathode.

Calendaring

This dry cathode is compacted through R2R calendaring to reduce the thickness and increase the density of the cathode active layer, improving the electrochemical performance and energy density of the final SSB.

Cutting

The electrode is cut with the specific dimensions for coin cells and monocoils.

Figure 17 - Process flow of the wet cathode processing.

Cathode dry processing

This process consists of the production of the solid-state positive electrode by dry processing and consists of the following steps (Figure 18):

Mixing

It consists of mixing the materials until they are homogeneous.

Extrusion:

The mixture obtained in the mixing is inserted in the extruder. The mixture goes down through a “barrel holding the screw within it”. The ionic liquid is added to the mixture through a liquid dozer of the extruder, and finally, a solid compacted mixture (extrudate) is obtained.

Coating

Batches of the mixture are inserted on top of the gap between the first and second rollers and then coated on the carbon-coated aluminium foil inserted from the third roller. In the end, a cathode foil is obtained.

Figure 18 - Process flow of the dry cathode processing.

Electrolyte production

This process consists of the production of the electrolyte. This process includes the following steps (Figure 19):

Solubilisation

The preparation of a gel polymer solution involves utilising magnetic stirring. Initially, polymer is dissolved in a solvent by stirring, resulting in solution A.

Mixing

Concurrently, plasticisers and lithium salts are mixed separately in solvent to form solution B. Subsequently, solution B is gradually poured into solution A, and the combined mixture is stirred for an additional 2 hours at room temperature, producing the final gel polymer solution, referred to as solution C. This stepwise approach ensures the homogeneous integration of all components.

Coating

The casting of the gel polymer solution is executed using a bar coater to ensure uniform film formation. Initially, solution C is cast onto a PET liner. A porous separator is deposited onto the freshly coated surface within a few seconds. After allowing a few seconds for initial impregnation, solution C is again cast over the impregnated separator at a reduced speed and an increased coating. This precise and controlled casting process ensures the consistent layering and thorough integration of the gel polymer electrolyte with the separator, which is crucial for the performance and stability of the final product.

Drying

Drying at room temperature under argon flow.

Figure 19 - Process flow of the electrolyte processing.

Results and discussion

This section presents the environmental and cost assessment results of the work performed by the WP3 tasks. It is subdivided into two subsections: Environmental Assessment and Cost Assessment. The environmental assessment offers a comprehensive overview of the environmental footprint associated with the WP3 processes. Similarly, the cost assessment provides a thorough analysis from a cost perspective.

Environmental Assessment

This subsection presents the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results. The collected inventory was modelled in the life cycle database Ecoinvent v3.9.1 to match the quantified flows with existing processes in the database with the support of the LCA software tool SimaPro V9.5.0.0[34]. The quantified environmental impacts were analysed with the impact quantification method ReCiPe 2016 v1.1 Endpoint (H) level [6]. The analysis involved assessing the manufacturing process for each cell component, following a cradle-to-gate boundary approach. This study focused on assessing the environmental impact associated with the production of SSB cell components, in this context, the analysis did not consider the transport phase. In each process are presented the main results and observations together with the graphic results in ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method. The numerical values of the processes are in the annexes, along with graphic results in ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) method.

Due to high confidentiality concerns, no primary data was provided for polymer material production for this study. However, in order to overcome this, ARKEMA provided LCA results considering ReCiPe and 13 impact categories¹ using the Midpoint (H) method. Additionally, ARKEMA provided results for 12 impact categories² using the Endpoint (H) method. Therefore, cell components utilizing this material, such as the cathode and the electrolyte, were analysed exclusively through these impact categories.

¹ Global warming; Stratospheric ozone depletion; Ionizing radiation; Ozone formation, Human health; Fine particulate matter formation; Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems; Terrestrial acidification; Freshwater eutrophication; Marine eutrophication; Land use; Mineral resource scarcity; Fossil resource scarcity; Water consumption

² Global warming, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ionizing radiation, Ozone formation, Fine particulate matter formation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Land use, Mineral resource scarcity, Fossil resource scarcity, Water consumption

NMC powder production

Figure 20 presents the impacts associated with the NMC811 powder production process. This process, conducted by CPT in Norway, utilized the Norwegian electricity mix.

As illustrated in Figure 20 the solution production step is identified as the main impact contributor across nearly all impact categories, with contributions ranging from 35% to 99%, except for Ozone formation, where it was the second main impact contributor (4,3%). Spray pyrolysis was the main contributor to Ozone formation (94,6%).

The result of the solution production was mainly due to the consumption of CRM: nickel (11-93%), lithium (2-80%), and cobalt (3-49%). The second main contributor was annealing, with contributions between 1-29% (except for Ozone formation), due to the high energy consumption.

Figure 20 - Potential environmental impacts of NMC811 powder production in Pt (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Lithium-Metal anode production

Figure 21 presents the impacts of the Li-M anode process. This process consisted of two steps: Li-M deposition and protective layer deposition. Both Li-Metal deposition and protective layer deposition are performed using the same equipment, streamlining the overall process. This process was conducted by ABEE, located in Belgium, meaning that the Belgian electricity mix was used.

Li-M deposition is identified as the main impact contributor across all impact categories, with contributions ranging from 60% to 98%. This is mainly attributed to the consumption of copper (Cu), which occurs in significantly larger quantities compared to lithium during this process step.

Energy consumption data was unavailable as the specific coating material has not yet been finalised. This selection directly influences the amount of energy required for the process. Consequently, no environmental impacts associated with energy use are currently included.

Figure 21 - Potential environmental impacts of Li-M anode production in Pt (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Cathode wet processing

This process was performed by CIDETEC, located in Spain, so the electricity mix was Spanish. Figure 22 presents the impacts of the cathode wet processing. The cathode utilizes the polymer, for which the data is confidential, consequently, the impacts of the cathode wet processing were analysed across the 12 impact categories.

It's observed that mixing and drying steps are the main impact contributors of this process. The mixing is the main impact contributor in eight impact categories (Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ozone formation, Fine particulate matter formation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Mineral resource scarcity, Water consumption), around 45 to 98%. Drying is the main impact contributor in four impact categories (Global warming, Ionizing radiation, Land use and Fossil resource scarcity), with the participation of between 43-53% in these categories.

Figure 22 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Examining the mixing process more in-depth, depicted in Figure 23, it's observed that the reason for this result is the NMC811, more precisely Co and Ni, and electricity. The NMC811 is the main impact contributor in 10 impact categories (Global warming, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ozone formation, fine particle matter formation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Land use, Mineral resource scarcity, Water consumption) with a contribution between 51-97%. Electricity is the main contributor to Ionizing radiation and Fossil resource scarcity, with contributions of 59.9% and 50.5%, respectively, which is related to the electricity mix of the country, in this case, Spain.

Figure 23 - Potential environmental impacts of mixing step for cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H);

Examining the drying step, the main factor responsible for the high impact is energy consumption. This is related to the country's electricity mix. Note that, besides the input of the main product, electricity is the only input in this process step.

Cathode dry processing

Figure 24 presents the impacts of the cathode wet processing. This process was performed by TUBS, located in Germany, so the electricity mix was German. The cathode used a polymer with restricted data. As a result, the effects of the cathode dry processing were assessed in the 12 impact categories.

Figure 24 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing in Pt (FU = 0.3 kg) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

It is observed that the mixing step is the main impact contributor across all impact categories, with contributions ranging from 50% to 99%. Extrusion ranks as the second main impact contributor in all categories, with contributions ranging from 1% to 40%.

This result is due to the consumption of NMC811, more precisely, Co, Ni, and Li, in the mixing process depicted in Figure 25. This is observed in all impact categories with contributions above 90%.

Figure 25 - Potential environmental impacts of mixing step for cathode dry processing in Pt (FU = 0.3 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Electrolyte production

Figure 26 presents the impacts of the electrolyte processing. This process was carried out at ARKEMA's facilities in France, utilizing the French electricity mix. The electrolyte incorporated a polymer, for which limited information was made available. Consequently, the effects of the electrolyte processing were evaluated across the 12 impact categories.

Note that there isn't energy associated to the drying process. The main impact contributors of this process are solubilisation and mixing process steps. To understand these results, both of these processes will be examined in greater detail in Figure 27 and Figure 28. Solubilization is the main impact contributor in 11 impact categories, with participations between 60-72%, except in Marine eutrophication, where mixing is the main impact contributor (~ 47%).

Figure 26 - Potential environmental impacts of Electrolyte production in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Upon analysing the solubilisation step in Figure 27, it's apparent that energy consumption is the predominant impact contributor across nine categories. Exceptions include Freshwater eutrophication, where the polymer is the main contributor (56.7%). Regarding Fossil resource scarcity and Water consumption, the solvent is the main contributor, with impacts ranging from 45% to 52%.

Figure 27 - Potential environmental impacts of Solubilization step in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Examining the mixing step (Figure 28), it is observed that energy consumption is the main impact contributor across nine impact categories, with contributions around 51-99%, except for Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication and Water consumption, where the Li salt is the dominant contributor, with contributions between 39-55%.

Figure 28 - Potential environmental impacts of mixing step in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

In general, it's observed in these lab-scale processes that the main impact contributors are related to the consumption of CRM, such as Ni, Co and Cu, and energy consumption. Since they are small-scale, there isn't yet a clear idea of how energy-intensive these processes are since some steps were done manually and others are incomplete. Besides that, most of them didn't have residues and emissions reported, which can influence the impact results.

It's commonly observed in both of cathode dry and wet processing, that the mixing step has a higher impact because of the CAM (NMC811), CAM being the main responsible of the impact is something that has been reported in the literature [11], [13], [17], [18], [19], [20], [32].

It is important to note that the current results are based on lab-level data, where the processes have not yet been optimised. Consequently, the environmental impacts observed are expected to be higher due to the inefficiencies and increased waste generation inherent in laboratory-scale development.

Cost Assessment

This section presents the project's cost assessment results, performed following the MFCA methodology. These results were compiled and analysed in Excel worksheets, utilizing data gathered from project partners. The data was collected using SUNDIAL, through which the partners involved in the production process shared information about the materials and energy used. As a result, the analysis mainly used primary data, supplemented with secondary data in specific cases where primary data was unavailable. Secondary data used will be indicated in the following sections.

All monetary units were converted to euros based on the average exchange rate for 2023. The analysis considered different FU depending on the process analysed: it was selected as 1 kg of the product at each stage.

Besides that, it's important to note once again that all the data provided and used is based on lab-scale scenarios. Considering the concept of economy of scale, which says that the average cost per unit of production tends to decrease as the output volume increases, it's important to keep in mind that the results presented may not reflect the reality of industrialized battery production on a large scale [43].

NMC powder production

In Figure 29, the cost preliminary results for NMC powder production are shown. This process had a total cost of € 557.96, with € 79.79 attributed to wastes of the process. Please take note of the following considerations:

- The electricity prices used in the analysis were from Norway, as the production process was based there;
- For Oxygen the provided data indicated an O₂ annealing batch size of approximately 0.5-1 kg;
- To facilitate the analysis, some costs and prices had to be converted from NOK to EUR using the 2023 average exchange rate of 0.087 NOK/EUR [44];
- Although the analysis considered waste and by-products in the costs by tracking material flows, they were all aggregated for the total costs.

As illustrated, the major contributor to the costs is the annealing step, which contributes 61.2%. In this step, oxygen, a highly purified and expensive gas due to its production process, is introduced into the production process, contributing about 94% of the steps' cost [45].

The solution production step is the second largest contributor to the total costs, with 33.7%. In this step, the critical materials are introduced in the process, with nickel and lithium being the main ones responsible for the costs (47% and 35%, respectively). As previously mentioned, these materials tend to have high prices derived from their economic importance and supply risk [40]. In this case, the cobalt, mentioned in the baseline, even though it has the highest cost of the critical materials used in the NMC chemistries, has a relatively low contribution due to the small quantities used in the NMC 811.

Additionally, 14.3 % of the inputs convert into wastes, equating to 0.48 kg, which has € 55.91 associated with NMC caught in filters and disposed of and € 23.88 associated with wasted NMC powder as associated costs.

Figure 29 - Cost preliminary results NMC powder production (FU = 1 kg | 557.96 €/kg).

Lithium-Metal anode production

Figure 30 represents the costs associated with producing Lithium-Metal anode. This process had € 1150.45 in total costs, with no accounted wastes. The data provided for costs and prices is in USD. To facilitate and standardise the analysis, the values were converted to EUR using the average 2023 exchange rate of 0.924 USD/EUR [45].

As mentioned previously, energy consumption data was unavailable, as the choice of the specific coating material is yet to be determined. As a result, the costs related to energy consumption are not included in this step.

The analysis showed that the lithium deposition step is the major contributor to the total costs, accounting for 96.6 %. Within this step, the introduction of lithium in the system makes up most of the costs, contributing to 95.0 % of the steps' costs. Lithium, as already mentioned, is a critical material that has a high price derived from its criticality but also from its really high demand. As a result, despite the introduction of copper in larger quantities within this step, lithium continues to be the key cost driver because of its much higher cost.

Figure 30 - Cost preliminary results of anode Li-M production (FU = 1 kg | 1150.45 €/kg).

Cathode wet processing

Figure 31 presents the preliminary cost assessment results for the cathode wet processing. This process had € 720.40 in total costs and didn't account for waste. Some considerations were made, such as using electricity prices from Norway and converting NOK to EUR at a rate of 0.087 NOK/EUR, similar to the NMC powder production process [44]. Other than that, the price considered for the NMC811 input goes in accordance with the NMC powder production: 557.96 €/kg.

The analysis results show that mixing contributes the most to the total costs, with 90.5 %. Mixing is the costlier process step due to the usage of materials such as NMC811 and catholyte, which represent ~61% and 29% of the costs of the step, respectively.

As previously analysed, the costs associated with the NMC811 input are deeply connected to nickel and lithium. The high costs of ionic liquid are related to the complexity of the synthesis process and high-purity materials, which are also inflated by the specialized and niche market [46].

Figure 31 - Cost preliminary results of cathode wet fabrication (FU = 1 kg | 720.40 €/kg).

Cathode dry processing

Figure 32 presents the preliminary results for the cost assessment of cathode dry processing. The total cost for producing 1 kg of cathode through this process was € 542.43, not accounting for the costs associated with the waste generated. Please note the following considerations:

- The pricing information for carbon black and polymer used by the partner was unavailable. Therefore, costs of the same materials used in .
- Cathode wet processing and Electrolyte production, respectively, were used. This way, these two inputs rely on secondary cost data;
- The electricity price was not provided, so the average price of electricity for 2023 for Germany, where the production process takes place, was used: 95.2 €/MWh;

- Similar to Cathode wet processing, the input cost for NMC811 was aligned with the resulting price from NMC powder production: 557.96 €/kg.

For the results of the analysis, the mixing step was the costliest, contributing 76.8% to the costs of the process. The introduction of NMC811, the CAM, to the system was the major motive for this high contribution, accounting for about 89.7% of the costs of this step, due to, as previously mentioned, the high costs associated with this material, which includes CRMs.

The second-largest contributor is the extrusion step, which contributes 22% to the process's costs. This contribution is mainly derived from the introduction of ionic liquid to the system. As mentioned previously, this input, which contributes 73.6% of the step's costs, has high costs because of the complexity of its synthesis process and high-purity materials.

Figure 32 - Cost preliminary results of cathode dry fabrication (FU = 1 kg | 542.43 €/kg).

Electrolyte production

Figure 33 presents the preliminary results for the cost assessment of electrolyte production. This process had a total cost of € 55.69, with no wastes accounted for. When considering the prices, it's important to note that the figures provided by our partners are market prices and are not necessarily reflective of actual prices. Therefore, the electrolyte cost analysis does not rely on main cost data.

That said, the cost results showed that the major contributor to the total costs is the solubilisation step, which contributes about 46.7%. In this step, the energy utilized for the mixing is responsible for 77.0% of the steps' costs.

The second-largest cost contributor is the mixing step, which accounts for 30.4% of the total costs. Here too, energy consumption is significant, making up 59.1% of the mixing step costs. Both steps involve the introduction of materials into the system that have comparatively low prices, thereby amplifying the impact of the energy consumption-associated costs on the overall expenses of electrolyte production. The most expensive material introduced is the porous separator, inputted in the coating step, which contributes 98.6% to the steps' costs. In the drying step, no energy consumption was provided.

Figure 33 - Cost preliminary results of Electrolyte membrane production (FU = 1 kg | 55.70 €/kg).

The cost analysis of the initial results for the SPINMATE project shows that the main cost drivers are mostly linked to the CRMs. Additionally, the use of Oxygen in NMC powder production and electricity in Electrolyte production contributes significantly to the costs. It's important to note that these processes are currently being studied at a lab-scale, so the actual energy intensity is unclear. It's also worth noting that once these processes are industrialized and produced on a larger scale, the principle of economy of scale will come into play, leading to cost reductions as the processes are optimized. Furthermore, the lack of information on waste produced during the production process is also important to consider, as it can impact the observed results.

When comparing the two different processes for the cathode processing (wet and dry), the costs associated with the wet process are approximately 25% higher than the dry. This difference is justified by the usage of material and energy, in which, for 1 kg of cathode, the wet process consumes more of both compared to the dry process.

It is important to note that the current results are based on lab-level data, where the processes have not yet been optimised. As a result, the costs associated with these lab-scale processes are also expected to be higher due to the lack of economies of scale.

Conclusions

This deliverable aims to report the environmental and cost performance of the small-scale results of the SPINMATE small-scale processes. To date, this assessment focuses on WP3 preliminary results, more specifically on the production of cell components, such as anode, cathode and electrolyte. The information was collected between the M17-M22.

The analysis of the current literature gave relevant insights related to their development, environmental impacts, and costs. Research has predominantly focused on battery applications for electric vehicles, with many studies performing comparative analyses between different battery chemistries. This highlights the important role of batteries in the future of sustainable e-mobility.

In cradle-to-gate studies, one of the main findings is the significant environmental impact in the manufacturing phase, more precisely related to cell manufacturing. This is attributed to the raw materials used in NMCx cathodes: Li, Ni, and Co. These are identified as major contributors, with Co having the highest impact. The extraction and processing of these materials are crucial areas of concern due to their high environmental impacts.

Moreover, the country's electricity mix where the batteries are produced greatly influences the overall environmental impact. Countries with cleaner energy grids result in lower impact values for battery production, emphasizing the importance of regional energy policies in the sustainability of battery manufacturing.

The functional unit commonly used in battery life cycle assessments is kilowatt-hours (kWh). This unit captures batteries' core function of storing energy and provides a clear basis for comparing the environmental and cost implications of producing different energy storage capacities.

Cradle-to-grave studies concluded that recycling in the end-of-life phase makes a small contribution to the whole life. Yet, the use of recycled metal is recommended as a means to mitigate environmental impacts further.

In summary, the current literature research points to the manufacturing phase as the most impactful in cradle-to-gate studies, with raw materials playing a critical role in the overall environmental impacts. Country electricity mixes and recycling practices are relevant in shaping the sustainability of EV batteries. Continued advancements in these areas are essential for reducing the environmental impacts and improving the overall sustainability of EV battery technologies.

The analysis of current literature on cost aspects sheds light on the main contributors to LIB costs, particularly in electric vehicle applications, similarly to the environmental impacts focused ones. Notably, the studies selected underscore the significant dependence of battery costs on CRM prices, given their extensive use in AMs, high prices, and market volatility.

The materials represent a major part of the total costs, with special importance for the cathode materials and anode materials. Estimations for battery cell manufacturing hover around \$94 per kWh, while pack-level costs range from \$84 to \$432, with variations based on chemistry and production scale.

Multiple techniques can be employed for this analysis and estimation, with parametric and analytical—both quantitative—being the most common. For cost modelling, the BatPaC model is the most utilized and recognised among the scientific community.

Based on the literature and with the collaboration of SPINMATE partners, the battery chemistries for the baseline were selected, SoA baseline focused on batteries with similar chemistries to SPINMATE's (NMCx-graphite). The electrolyte chosen was "LiPF₆ + EC + DMC". Based on this, the following chemistries were selected for the baseline:

- NMC111-Graphite. Electrolyte: LiPF₆ + EC + DMC;
- NMC622-Graphite. Electrolyte: LiPF₆ + EC + DMC;
- NMC811-Graphite. Electrolyte: LiPF₆ + EC + DMC.

Additionally, the electricity mix selected was Chinese. This country was selected due to its market dominance in Li-ion batteries. This makes it a suitable representation of the current market, providing a fitting baseline for comparison/correlation.

Based on this selection, a model of the baseline for the environmental assessment was carried out using the specific impact method, ReCiPe. The modelling of these chemistries consistently showed that the battery cell had the most significant impact among all observed battery pack components, including the cooling system, packaging, BMS, and electricity consumption. These findings are aligned with the current literature. A deeper examination of the battery cell reveals that cathode production is the main driver of environmental impact. This is mainly due to the materials used, such as Ni, Co, and Li (CRMs).

For the cost assessment baseline, the BatPaC 5.1 Database was consulted along with the partners' inputs and validations. Taking into account the same chemistries as defined, the database provided detailed data on production costs, including costs associated with materials purchase and energy consumption, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the costs related to the three specified chemistries at the levels of cells, modules, and packs.

This analysis revealed that cell production significantly influences total costs, with CAM (NMC111, NMC622, and NMC811) emerging as the main contributor across all three chemistries analysed. This can be explained by the inclusion of critical materials in the CAM, which carry high prices due to supply risks and economic importance. Additionally, the high demand for some of these materials also contributes to their high costs. Therefore, the conclusions drawn from the literature review align with the ones from the baseline.

Regarding SPINMATE's cell components environmental assessment, the assessment followed the standardized methodology mentioned in the SPINMATE - Sustainability performance and cost assessment methodology chapter. The assessment consisted of analysing the manufacturing process of each cell component resulting from WP3: anode, cathode, and electrolyte. Through continuous collaboration and communication with partners, accurate and robust LCI data was collected, allowing for LCA and cost models to be created with the support of the DDP.

The environmental impacts were quantified based on the country manufacturer's electricity mix data from life cycle databases. The ReCiPe impact quantification method was selected and the environmental impacts were translated into endpoints (ecopoints) quantified and analysed for each process. The cost analysis, on the other hand, quantified the inputs and outputs based on the data provided by the partners and cost databases. The MFCA methodology was selected and the costs were studied associated to material and energy flows throughout the production processes, accounting for wastes and by-products when the data was available to do so.

Concerning the environmental assessment of the preliminary results, the solution production step was the main impact contributor in the analysis of the NMC811 powder production. This

result is associated mainly with the consumption of materials such as Co and Ni. Spray pyrolysis also presents a relevant impact on energy consumption.

Regarding the anode production, Li-M deposition and protective layer deposition are conducted using the same equipment. Li-M deposition is the main contributor to impact across all categories (accounting for 60-98% of the impact). This significant impact is primarily due to this step's high consumption of copper, which is used in larger quantities compared to lithium. Currently, energy consumption data is unavailable as the specific coating material has not been decided. The choice of coating material will directly affect the energy requirements for the process. As a result, environmental impacts related to energy use are not yet included in the assessment.

Regarding the cathode wet processing, the analysis showed that the mixing and drying steps are the main contributors to environmental impacts in this process. Mixing is the leading impact contributor in 8 impact categories, ranging between 45-98% of the impacts. Drying is the dominant impact contributor in four categories, with contributions between 43-53%, in these categories, which was mainly associated with energy consumption. Analysing the mixing process reveals that the significant impact is primarily due to the materials used, specifically the AM (NMC811) due to Co and Ni. This influence is evident in 10 impact categories, with contributions exceeding 51%.

In the cathode dry processing, the analysis showed that the mixing step is the main impact contributor in all impact categories, with contributions between 50% and 99%. This is related to the consumption of Co and Ni in the CAM, with contributions above 90%.

In electrolyte production, the main impact contributors are the solubilisation and mixing steps. Solubilisation dominates in 11 impact categories, ranging between 62-72%, except for Marine eutrophication (where mixing takes precedence with contributions exceeding 50%). Energy consumption is identified as the main responsible behind these results for both of these process steps (solubilisation and mixing).

Correlation of the SPINMATE results with the selected baseline at the cell component level demonstrates that, in both scenarios, the CAM is the main contributor to the cathode's environmental impact, mainly due to the presence of Co and Ni. This consistent influence of these materials is observed across both cases. Correlations regarding the anode and electrolyte cannot yet be established, as they employ materials that differ from those documented in the literature.

Concerning the cost analysis of the preliminary results, the NMC powder production results revealed that the annealing step was the major contributor to the costs (~61%), highly associated with the use of Oxygen, a high-purity expansive gas. The solution production step is the second most significant contributor, accounting for approximately 34%. This is due to the introduction of several critical materials in the system, such as Ni and Li, which are major cost factors in this step.

The Lithium-Metal anode production has the Li-M deposition step as the main contributor, with more than 90% of the total costs of the process. This is caused by the introduction of lithium in the system, a critical material with high prices caused by its high demand and criticality. As already mentioned, there's a lack of data concerning energy consumption since the specific coating material has not been decided. When this is included, the costs associated with this process will increase, possibly changing the proportions of the contribution of each step.

For the Cathode wet processing, the mixing step was revealed as the main contributor (~90%) due to NMC811 and the catholyte inputs. Both constituents are relatively expensive: NMC811 due

to its inclusion of critical materials and catholyte due to the ionic liquid, which involves a complex synthesis process and requires high-purity materials.

For the Cathode dry processing, similar to the cathode wet processing, the mixing step is the main contributor to the costs, with ~77%. The introduction of the NMC811 in the system is the cause of this high contribution. The second most significant contributor is the extrusion step, which accounts for 22% of the impact due to the inclusion of an ionic liquid. The explanation for this aligns with what was already mentioned: the high prices of these materials. Comparing the two cathode processing methods, wet has higher costs than dry, which is justified by the higher consumption of materials and energy of the first.

For the Electrolyte production process, the solubilisation step is the most significant contributor (~47%), followed by the mixing step (~30%). Both phases have energy consumption as the main responsible for its costs, since the materials introduced in the system within the process have a comparatively low cost.

This way, the preliminary results for the SPINMATE project show that the main contributors to the costs of the whole process are majorly linked to the CRMs that are introduced in the system along the production process. Besides, oxygen and electricity also play important roles in some analysed processes. Once again, it is important to emphasize that as production becomes industrialized and scaled up, the principle of economies of scale will take effect, resulting in cost reductions.

When comparing these results to the chosen baseline at the cell level, it is clear that the CRMs are the main cost drivers in all scenarios. In the baseline scenario, the CRMs introduced by the cathode are the main contributors to the costs. However, in the project results, when comparing 1 kg of cathode to 1 kg of anode, the CRMs of the anode are the major cost contributors, as the anode results have higher costs. It is important to note that once the cell is assembled, the quantities of cathode and anode included in the system will likely be different, leading to variations in the contributions of each.

It needs to be noted that this study has limitations, such as:

- The processes have manual steps, resulting in negligible energy consumption. Furthermore, the processes lack optimisation;
- Certain processes, particularly regarding the anode, remain incomplete, and the associated impacts of energy consumption are not fully representable;
- The processes under investigation are conducted at a laboratory scale and do not reflect industrial-scale operations.

Overall, it was possible to identify the main hotspots for each cell component. The environmental and cost assessments allowed to identify the process steps responsible for the higher impacts and costs, as well as the main inputs responsible for those results, such as materials and energy sources. These results are informative and can support partners' decision-making.

Additionally, the literature review provided early insights into the potential key hotspots of LIB impacts. Notably, the cathode emerged as a significant contributor, with the cathode active material accounting for most of the impacts. The same results were observed in the SPINMATE's project. Further studies are necessary to understand the impacts of the battery cell as a whole since, for now, only cell components were evaluated individually.

It is important to note that these results are at the lab-level. Consequently, the environmental impacts are expected to be higher due to the non-optimization of some processes and increased

waste generation typical of lab-scale development. Similarly, the costs are also anticipated to be elevated, given the absence of economies of scale. Further refinement and scaling up of these processes will likely result in reduced environmental impacts and lower costs.

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Annexes

Life Cycle Inventory

Baseline

The inventories used were from Ecoinvent v3.9.1 life cycle database. for a battery-pack of 23.5 kWh and 165 kg of mass [18].

NMC111

Table 22 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC111 battery pack [18].

I/O	Unit	Quantity	Ecoinvent
Materials			
Aluminium	kg	0.13653	Aluminium. wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium. wrought alloy Cut-off. U
Battery cell	kg	0.72591	Battery cell. Li-ion. NMC111 {CN} battery cell production. Li-ion. NMC111 Cut-off. U
BMS	kg	0.02424	Battery management system. for Li-ion battery {GLO} battery management system production. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Packaging	kg	0.0549	Battery module packaging. Li-ion {GLO} market for battery module packaging. Li-ion Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.00055	Copper. anode {GLO} market for copper. anode Cut-off. U
Electronic Components	kg	0.0043	Electronic component. passive. unspecified {GLO} market for electronic component. passive. unspecified Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.02151	Ethylene glycol {GLO} market for ethylene glycol Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.00018	Glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded {GLO} market for glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.135315	Impact extrusion of aluminium. 1 stroke {GLO} market for impact extrusion of aluminium. 1 stroke Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.00419	Polyethylene. high density. granulate {GLO} market for polyethylene. high density. granulate Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00618	Reinforcing steel {GLO} market for reinforcing steel Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.001215	Sheet rolling. aluminium {GLO} market for sheet rolling. aluminium Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00055	Sheet rolling. copper {GLO} market for sheet rolling. copper Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00618	Sheet rolling. steel {GLO} market for sheet rolling. steel Cut-off. U
Water	kg	0.02151	Tap water {RoW} market for tap water Cut-off. U
Electricity	kWh	0.00028	Electricity. medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity. medium voltage Cut-off. U

Table 23 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC111 battery cell [18].

I/O	Unit	Quantity	Ecoinvent
Materials			
Aluminium	kg	0.03	Aluminium collector foil. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for aluminium collector foil. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Aluminium	kg	0.0283	Aluminium. wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium. wrought alloy Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.2	Anode. graphite. for Li-ion battery {CN} market for anode. graphite. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Battery separator	kg	0.02	Battery separator {GLO} market for battery separator Cut-off. U
Cathode	kg	0.41	Cathode. NMC111. for Li-ion battery {CN} market for cathode. NMC111. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Copper	kg	0.12	Copper collector foil. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for copper collector foil. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.0335	Copper. anode {GLO} market for copper. anode Cut-off. U
Electrolyte	kg	0.146	Electrolyte. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for electrolyte. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.0041	Extrusion. plastic film {GLO} market for extrusion. plastic film Cut-off. U
Polymers	kg	0.0028	Polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous {GLO} market for polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous Cut-off. U
Polymers	kg	0.0013	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for polypropylene. granulate Cut-off. U
Aluminium	kg	0.0283	Sheet rolling. aluminium {GLO} market for sheet rolling. aluminium Cut-off. U
Copper	kg	0.0335	Sheet rolling. copper {GLO} market for sheet rolling. copper Cut-off. U
Energy	MJ	12.51	Heat. district or industrial. natural gas {RoW} market for heat. district or industrial. natural gas Cut-off. U
Energy	kWh	1.1875	Electricity. medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity. medium voltage Cut-off. U

NMC622

Table 24 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC622 battery pack [18].

I/O	Unit	Quantity	Ecoinvent
Materials			
Aluminium	kg	0.13653	Aluminium. wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium. wrought alloy Cut-off. U
Battery cell	kg	0.72591	Proxy for Battery cell. Li-ion, NMC622 {CN} battery cell production
BMS	kg	0.02424	Battery management system. for Li-ion battery {GLO} battery management system production. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Packaging	kg	0.0549	Battery module packaging. Li-ion {GLO} market for battery module packaging. Li-ion Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.00055	Copper. anode {GLO} market for copper. anode Cut-off. U
Electronic Components	kg	0.0043	Electronic component. passive. unspecified {GLO} market for electronic component. passive. unspecified Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.02151	Ethylene glycol {GLO} market for ethylene glycol Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.00018	Glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded {GLO} market for glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.135315	Impact extrusion of aluminium. 1 stroke {GLO} market for impact extrusion of aluminium. 1 stroke Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.00419	Injection moulding {GLO} market for injection moulding Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	1.41E-09	Polyethylene. high density. granulate {GLO} market for polyethylene. high density. granulate Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00419	Reinforcing steel {GLO} market for reinforcing steel Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00618	Sheet rolling. aluminium {GLO} market for sheet rolling. aluminium Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.001215	Sheet rolling. copper {GLO} market for sheet rolling. copper Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00055	Sheet rolling. steel {GLO} market for sheet rolling. steel Cut-off. U
Water	kg	0.00618	Tap water {RoW} market for tap water Cut-off. U
Electricity	kWh	0.00028	Electricity. medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity. medium voltage Cut-off. U

Table 25 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC622 battery cell [18].

I/O	Unit	Quantity	Ecoinvent
Materials			
Aluminium	kg	0.03	Aluminium collector foil. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for aluminium collector foil. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Aluminium	kg	0.0283	Aluminium. wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium. wrought alloy Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.2	Anode. graphite. for Li-ion battery {CN} market for anode. graphite. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Battery separator	kg	0.02	Battery separator {GLO} market for battery separator Cut-off. U
Cathode	kg	0.41	Proxy for Cathode. NMC111. for Li-ion battery {CN}
Copper	kg	0.12	Copper collector foil. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for copper collector foil. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.0335	Copper. anode {GLO} market for copper. anode Cut-off. U
Electrolyte	kg	0.146	Electrolyte. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for electrolyte. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.0041	Extrusion. plastic film {GLO} market for extrusion. plastic film Cut-off. U
Polymers	kg	0.0028	Polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous {GLO} market for polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous Cut-off. U
Polymers	kg	0.0013	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for polypropylene. granulate Cut-off. U
Aluminium	kg	0.0283	Sheet rolling. aluminium {GLO} market for sheet rolling. aluminium Cut-off. U
Copper	kg	0.0335	Sheet rolling. copper {GLO} market for sheet rolling. copper Cut-off. U
Energy	MJ	12.51	Heat. district or industrial. natural gas {RoW} market for heat. district or industrial. natural gas Cut-off. U
Energy	kWh	1.1875	Electricity. medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity. medium voltage Cut-off. U

NMC811

Table 26 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC811 battery pack [18].

I/O	Unit	Quantity	Ecoinvent
Materials			
Aluminium	kg	0.14283	Aluminium. wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium. wrought alloy Cut-off. U
Battery cell	kg	0.71359	Battery cell. Li-ion. NMC811 {CN} battery cell production. Li-ion. NMC811 Cut-off. U
BMS	kg	0.02426	Battery management system. for Li-ion battery {GLO} battery management system production. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Packaging	kg	0.05718	Battery module packaging. Li-ion {GLO} market for battery module packaging. Li-ion Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.001	Copper. anode {GLO} market for copper. anode Cut-off. U
Electronic Components	kg	0.00431	Electronic component. passive. unspecified {GLO} market for electronic component. passive. unspecified Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.02302	Ethylene glycol {GLO} market for ethylene glycol Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.00033	Glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded {GLO} market for glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.141616	Impact extrusion of aluminium. 1 stroke {GLO} market for impact extrusion of aluminium. 1 stroke Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.00405	Injection moulding {GLO} market for injection moulding Cut-off. U
Polymer	kg	0.00405	Polyethylene. high density. granulate {GLO} market for polyethylene. high density. granulate Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	1.48E-09	Metal working factory {GLO} market for metal working factory Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00642	Reinforcing steel {GLO} market for reinforcing steel Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.001214	Sheet rolling. aluminium {GLO} market for sheet rolling. aluminium Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.001	Sheet rolling. copper {GLO} market for sheet rolling. copper Cut-off. U
Precious metal	kg	0.00642	Sheet rolling. steel {GLO} market for sheet rolling. steel Cut-off. U
Water	kg	0.02302	Tap water {RoW} market for tap water Cut-off. U
Electricity	kWh	0.00028	Electricity. medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity. medium voltage Cut-off. U

Table 27 - Manufacturing of 1 kg of NMC811 battery cell [18].

I/O	Unit	Quantity	Ecoinvent
Materials			Battery. Li-ion. NMC811. rechargeable. prismatic {CN} battery production. Li-ion. NMC811. rechargeable. prismatic Cut-off. U
Aluminium	kg	0.0284	Aluminium collector foil. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for aluminium collector foil. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Aluminium	kg	0.0284	Aluminium. wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium. wrought alloy Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.2181	Anode. silicon coated graphite. for Li-ion battery {CN} market for anode. silicon coated graphite. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Battery separator	kg	0.0182	Battery separator {GLO} market for battery separator Cut-off. U
Cathode	kg	0.3773	Cathode. NMC811. for Li-ion battery {CN} market for cathode. NMC811. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Copper	kg	0.1243	Copper collector foil. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for copper collector foil. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Anode	kg	0.033	Copper. anode {GLO} market for copper. anode Cut-off. U
Electrolyte	kg	0.1683	Electrolyte. for Li-ion battery {GLO} market for electrolyte. for Li-ion battery Cut-off. U
Polymers	kg	0.004	Extrusion. plastic film {GLO} market for extrusion. plastic film Cut-off. U
Polymers	kg	0.0028	Polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous {GLO} market for polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous Cut-off. U
Polymers	kg	0.0012	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for polypropylene. granulate Cut-off. U
Aluminium	kg	0.0284	Sheet rolling. aluminium {GLO} market for sheet rolling. aluminium Cut-off. U
Copper	kg	0.033	Sheet rolling. copper {GLO} market for sheet rolling. copper Cut-off. U
Energy			
Energy	MJ	13.291	Heat. district or industrial. natural gas {RoW} market for heat. district or industrial. natural gas Cut-off. U
Energy	kWh	1.2616	Electricity. medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity. medium voltage Cut-off. U

Life Cycle Impact Assessment results

Baseline

NMC111

Table 28 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Battery cells	BMS	Packaging	Electronic components	Electricity	Polymers	Precious metals	Water	Total
Global warming	1.49E+00	9.49E-02	1.22E-01	2.92E-02	1.34E-02	6.10E-03	2.18E-01	2.53E-06	1.98E+00
Stratospheric ozone depletion	4.18E-04	2.64E-05	2.31E-05	8.32E-06	2.29E-06	5.88E-07	2.41E-05	8.04E-10	5.03E-04
Ionizing radiation	2.00E-04	6.62E-06	4.44E-06	2.02E-06	1.21E-06	1.74E-07	2.65E-06	1.57E-10	2.17E-04
Ozone formation	1.34E-02	1.08E-03	1.30E-03	4.09E-04	6.75E-05	4.06E-05	1.76E-03	1.90E-08	1.80E-02
Fine particulate matter formation	3.28E+00	1.77E-01	2.22E-01	5.93E-02	1.07E-02	4.59E-03	2.86E-01	3.33E-06	4.04E+00
Terrestrial acidification	5.20E-02	2.21E-03	2.99E-03	7.79E-04	1.05E-04	5.48E-05	3.59E-03	3.10E-08	6.17E-02
Freshwater eutrophication,	2.28E-03	2.04E-04	1.34E-04	6.31E-05	1.66E-05	1.79E-06	7.86E-05	1.10E-09	2.78E-03
Marine eutrophication	3.53E-06	6.52E-08	5.30E-08	2.06E-08	3.46E-08	1.49E-09	2.48E-08	2.72E-13	3.73E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1.37E-02	4.04E-04	4.06E-04	5.32E-05	1.20E-06	6.54E-07	1.29E-04	7.11E-10	1.47E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	3.94E-05	1.05E-05	7.23E-06	3.80E-06	1.79E-07	2.56E-08	2.44E-06	1.34E-11	6.36E-05
Marine ecotoxicity	6.08E-05	9.59E-06	8.22E-06	4.22E-06	4.11E-08	8.13E-09	1.09E-06	6.14E-12	8.39E-05
Human carcinogenic toxicity	1.31E-01	1.45E-02	2.30E-02	6.15E-03	2.45E-04	7.52E-05	3.51E-02	8.20E-08	2.10E-01
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	8.11E-01	3.61E-02	4.22E-02	7.52E-03	4.81E-04	1.18E-04	3.00E-02	1.35E-07	9.27E-01
Land use	4.50E-03	3.37E-04	3.56E-04	1.46E-04	2.60E-05	4.27E-06	1.94E-04	3.54E-09	5.56E-03
Mineral resource scarcity	2.05E-02	4.89E-04	5.14E-04	2.30E-04	3.58E-07	1.58E-07	2.84E-04	4.99E-10	2.20E-02
Fossil resource scarcity	4.80E-02	2.36E-03	2.57E-03	7.91E-04	3.08E-04	5.64E-04	3.47E-03	5.36E-08	5.81E-02
Water consumption	2.40E-01	7.16E-04	9.51E-04	2.60E-04	-2.64E-04	1.54E-04	1.25E-03	5.83E-06	2.43E-01
Total	6.110185851	0.32995277	0.418507406	0.104935856	0.025084719	0.01170482	0.580184611	1.2013E-05	7.580568

Table 29 -Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery cell in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Anode	Battery separator	Cathode. NMC111	Copper	Electrolyte	Energy	Polymers	Aluminium	Total
Global warming	1.15E-01	5.72E-02	9.80E-01	8.00E-02	5.35E-02	1.34E-01	9.53E-04	7.30E-02	1.49E+00
Stratospheric ozone depletion	2.33E-05	9.33E-06	3.01E-04	4.91E-05	7.29E-06	1.65E-05	2.51E-06	8.65E-06	4.18E-04
Ionizing radiation	3.09E-06	2.93E-06	1.83E-04	5.37E-06	2.08E-06	2.50E-06	1.91E-08	1.05E-06	2.00E-04
Ozone formation	1.76E-03	4.28E-04	7.18E-03	2.14E-03	3.81E-04	9.26E-04	6.19E-06	5.76E-04	1.34E-02
Fine particulate matter formation	6.21E-01	5.94E-02	1.46E+00	8.83E-01	6.64E-02	9.49E-02	6.27E-04	9.18E-02	3.28E+00
Terrestrial acidification	1.02E-02	6.15E-04	2.29E-02	1.50E-02	9.17E-04	1.17E-03	8.35E-06	1.14E-03	5.20E-02
Freshwater eutrophication,	8.85E-05	2.05E-05	1.77E-03	2.84E-04	6.76E-05	2.17E-05	2.97E-07	2.59E-05	2.28E-03
Marine eutrophication	5.88E-08	3.51E-09	3.21E-06	9.58E-08	1.50E-07	3.85E-09	2.58E-10	8.66E-09	3.53E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	2.74E-03	5.03E-06	4.27E-03	6.55E-03	7.09E-05	7.92E-06	3.08E-07	2.35E-05	1.37E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	4.47E-06	1.36E-07	2.08E-05	1.23E-05	6.91E-07	2.02E-07	6.11E-09	7.49E-07	3.94E-05
Marine ecotoxicity	1.19E-05	5.44E-08	1.93E-05	2.87E-05	4.32E-07	8.24E-08	2.58E-09	2.70E-07	6.08E-05
Human carcinogenic toxicity	2.35E-02	7.55E-04	3.74E-02	5.66E-02	1.19E-03	1.31E-03	1.56E-05	1.06E-02	1.31E-01
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	2.03E-01	1.99E-03	1.10E-01	4.78E-01	5.80E-03	3.76E-03	1.96E-05	8.24E-03	8.11E-01
Land use	6.74E-04	8.12E-05	1.98E-03	1.48E-03	1.32E-04	9.06E-05	6.51E-07	6.21E-05	4.50E-03
Mineral resource scarcity	5.92E-04	7.30E-07	1.80E-02	1.71E-03	6.58E-05	8.77E-07	9.43E-08	8.36E-05	2.05E-02
Fossil resource scarcity	4.39E-03	1.40E-03	3.35E-02	1.87E-03	2.46E-03	3.13E-03	9.05E-05	1.18E-03	4.80E-02
Water consumption	1.36E-03	3.12E-04	2.32E-01	3.74E-03	1.17E-03	2.36E-04	1.86E-05	4.78E-04	2.40E-01
Total	9.84E-01	1.22E-01	2.91E+00	1.53E+00	1.32E-01	2.40E-01	1.74E-03	1.87E-01	6.11E+00

Table 30 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack (numerical) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

Impact category	Battery cells	BMS	Packaging	Electronic components	Electricity	Polymers	Precious metals	Water
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	9.20E+01	5.85E+00	7.52E+00	1.80E+00	8.26E-01	3.76E-01	1.34E+01	1.56E-04
Stratospheric ozone depletion (kg CFC11 eq)	4.72E-05	2.98E-06	2.61E-06	9.40E-07	2.58E-07	6.64E-08	2.72E-06	9.07E-11
Ionizing radiation (kBq Co-60 eq)	1.41E+00	4.67E-02	3.13E-02	1.43E-02	8.53E-03	1.23E-03	1.87E-02	1.11E-06
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	2.62E-01	2.09E-02	2.52E-02	7.79E-03	1.32E-03	7.79E-04	3.48E-02	3.74E-07
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	3.13E-01	1.69E-02	2.12E-02	5.66E-03	1.02E-03	4.38E-04	2.73E-02	3.17E-07
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	2.70E-01	2.18E-02	2.62E-02	8.35E-03	1.36E-03	8.26E-04	3.53E-02	3.81E-07
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	9.07E-01	3.86E-02	5.21E-02	1.36E-02	1.83E-03	9.56E-04	6.27E-02	5.40E-07
Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq)	1.26E-02	1.13E-03	7.42E-04	3.48E-04	9.18E-05	9.86E-06	4.34E-04	6.05E-09
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	7.66E-03	1.42E-04	1.15E-04	4.47E-05	7.52E-05	3.24E-06	5.39E-05	5.90E-10
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	4.43E+03	1.31E+02	1.32E+02	1.72E+01	3.91E-01	2.12E-01	4.19E+01	2.31E-04
Freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	2.10E-01	5.61E-02	3.86E-02	2.03E-02	9.54E-04	1.36E-04	1.30E-02	7.13E-08
Marine ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	2.14E+00	3.38E-01	2.89E-01	1.48E-01	1.45E-03	2.86E-04	3.82E-02	2.16E-07
Human carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	2.37E+00	2.61E-01	4.16E-01	1.11E-01	4.43E-03	1.36E-03	6.34E-01	1.48E-06
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity(kg 1.4-DCB)	2.14E+02	9.49E+00	1.11E+01	1.98E+00	1.26E-01	3.10E-02	7.90E+00	3.56E-05
Land use (m2a crop eq)	1.87E+00	1.41E-01	1.49E-01	6.09E-02	1.08E-02	1.78E-03	8.08E-02	1.48E-06
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu eq)	1.24E+01	2.96E-01	3.12E-01	1.40E-01	2.17E-04	9.56E-05	1.72E-01	3.02E-07
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	2.46E+01	1.50E+00	1.75E+00	4.79E-01	1.79E-01	2.12E-01	2.78E+00	3.73E-05
Water consumption (m3)	6.15E+00	4.80E-02	5.41E-02	1.51E-02	-2.77E-03	4.25E-03	7.62E-02	1.44E-04

Figure 34 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC111 battery pack (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

NMC622

Table 31 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Battery cells	BMS	Packaging	Electronic components	Electricity	Polymers	Precious metals	Water	Total
Global warming	1.349253293	0.094933	0.122138	0.029207	0.013405	0.006098	0.21805	2.53E-06	1.833087
Stratospheric ozone depletion	0.000377845	2.64E-05	2.31E-05	8.32E-06	2.29E-06	5.88E-07	2.41E-05	8.04E-10	0.000463
Ionizing radiation	0.000176874	6.62E-06	4.44E-06	2.02E-06	1.21E-06	1.74E-07	2.65E-06	1.57E-10	0.000194
Ozone formation	0.012694917	0.001078	0.001297	0.000409	6.75E-05	4.06E-05	0.001761	1.9E-08	0.017349
Fine particulate matter formation	3.25177265	0.176635	0.221922	0.059304	0.010689	0.004593	0.286224	3.33E-06	4.011143
Terrestrial acidification	0.052089752	0.002212	0.002987	0.000779	0.000105	5.48E-05	0.003592	3.1E-08	0.06182
Freshwater eutrophication,	0.002199524	0.000204	0.000134	6.31E-05	1.66E-05	1.79E-06	7.86E-05	1.1E-09	0.002698
Marine eutrophication	3.39649E-06	6.52E-08	5.3E-08	2.06E-08	3.46E-08	1.49E-09	2.48E-08	2.72E-13	3.6E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	0.01337217	0.000404	0.000406	5.32E-05	1.2E-06	6.54E-07	0.000129	7.11E-10	0.014367
Freshwater ecotoxicity	3.73254E-05	1.05E-05	7.23E-06	3.8E-06	1.79E-07	2.56E-08	2.44E-06	1.34E-11	6.15E-05
Marine ecotoxicity	5.93979E-05	9.59E-06	8.22E-06	4.22E-06	4.11E-08	8.13E-09	1.09E-06	6.14E-12	8.26E-05
Human carcinogenic toxicity	0.126583815	0.014459	0.023036	0.006151	0.000245	7.52E-05	0.035095	8.2E-08	0.205645
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	0.797750266	0.036072	0.042156	0.007522	0.000481	0.000118	0.030024	1.35E-07	0.914123
Land use	0.004292713	0.000337	0.000356	0.000146	2.6E-05	4.27E-06	0.000194	3.54E-09	0.005357
Mineral resource scarcity	0.018395486	0.000489	0.000514	0.00023	3.58E-07	1.58E-07	0.000284	4.99E-10	0.019914
Fossil resource scarcity	0.042183046	0.002361	0.002566	0.000791	0.000308	0.000564	0.003469	5.36E-08	0.052241
Water consumption	0.209942056	0.000716	0.000951	0.00026	-0.00026	0.000154	0.001253	5.83E-06	0.213018
Total	5.881184525	0.329953	0.418507	0.104936	0.025085	0.011705	0.580184	1.2E-05	7.351566

Table 32 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery cell in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Anode	Battery separator	Cathode. NMC622	Copper	Electrolyte	Energy	Polymers	Aluminium	Total
Global warming	0.114714	0.0572427	0.835471	0.079967	0.053539	0.134374	0.000953	0.072993	1.349253
Stratospheric ozone depletion	2.33E-05	9.32599E-06	0.000261	4.91E-05	7.29E-06	1.65E-05	2.51E-06	8.65E-06	0.000378
Ionizing radiation	3.09E-06	2.93221E-06	0.00016	5.37E-06	2.08E-06	2.5E-06	1.91E-08	1.05E-06	0.000177
Ozone formation	0.001763	0.000428206	0.00648	0.002135	0.000381	0.000926	6.19E-06	0.000576	0.012695
Fine particulate matter formation	0.620576	0.059369682	1.435346	0.882814	0.066406	0.094859	0.000627	0.091774	3.251773
Terrestrial acidification	0.010171	0.000614818	0.023041	0.015031	0.000917	0.001171	8.35E-06	0.001136	0.05209
Freshwater eutrophication,	8.85E-05	2.04851E-05	0.001691	0.000284	6.76E-05	2.17E-05	2.97E-07	2.59E-05	0.0022
Marine eutrophication	5.88E-08	3.51485E-09	3.08E-06	9.58E-08	1.5E-07	3.85E-09	2.58E-10	8.66E-09	3.4E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	0.002742	5.03004E-06	0.003974	0.00655	7.09E-05	7.92E-06	3.08E-07	2.35E-05	0.013372
Freshwater ecotoxicity	4.47E-06	1.36491E-07	1.87E-05	1.23E-05	6.91E-07	2.02E-07	6.11E-09	7.49E-07	3.73E-05
Marine ecotoxicity	1.19E-05	5.44238E-08	1.8E-05	2.87E-05	4.32E-07	8.24E-08	2.58E-09	2.7E-07	5.94E-05
Human carcinogenic toxicity	0.023457	0.000755159	0.03269	0.056594	0.001192	0.001312	1.56E-05	0.010568	0.126584
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	0.203303	0.001992437	0.096266	0.478366	0.005804	0.003761	1.96E-05	0.008238	0.79775
Land use	0.000674	8.12442E-05	0.001776	0.001477	0.000132	9.06E-05	6.51E-07	6.21E-05	0.004293
Mineral resource scarcity	0.000592	7.29882E-07	0.015942	0.00171	6.58E-05	8.77E-07	9.43E-08	8.36E-05	0.018395
Fossil resource scarcity	0.004392	0.001404155	0.027654	0.001874	0.002456	0.003134	9.05E-05	0.001178	0.042183
Water consumption	0.001362	0.000311848	0.202628	0.003736	0.001172	0.000236	1.86E-05	0.000478	0.209942
Total	0.983875	0.122238947	2.68342	1.530633	0.132215	0.239914	0.001743	0.187146	5.881185

Table 33 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack (numerical) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

Impact category	Battery cells	BMS	Packaging	Electronic components	Electricity	Polymers	Precious metals	Water
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	8.31E+01	5.85E+00	7.52E+00	1.80E+00	8.26E-01	3.76E-01	1.34E+01	1.56E-04
Stratospheric ozone depletion (kg CFC11 eq)	4.27E-05	2.98E-06	2.61E-06	9.40E-07	2.58E-07	6.64E-08	2.72E-06	9.07E-11
Ionizing radiation (kBq Co-60 eq)	1.25E+00	4.67E-02	3.13E-02	1.43E-02	8.53E-03	1.23E-03	1.87E-02	1.11E-06
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	2.49E-01	2.09E-02	2.52E-02	7.79E-03	1.32E-03	7.79E-04	3.48E-02	3.74E-07
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	3.10E-01	1.69E-02	2.12E-02	5.66E-03	1.02E-03	4.38E-04	2.73E-02	3.17E-07
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	2.56E-01	2.18E-02	2.62E-02	8.35E-03	1.36E-03	8.26E-04	3.53E-02	3.81E-07
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	9.09E-01	3.86E-02	5.21E-02	1.36E-02	1.83E-03	9.56E-04	6.27E-02	5.40E-07
Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq)	1.21E-02	1.13E-03	7.42E-04	3.48E-04	9.18E-05	9.86E-06	4.34E-04	6.05E-09
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	7.38E-03	1.42E-04	1.15E-04	4.47E-05	7.52E-05	3.24E-06	5.39E-05	5.90E-10
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	4.33E+03	1.31E+02	1.32E+02	1.72E+01	3.91E-01	2.12E-01	4.19E+01	2.31E-04
Freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	1.99E-01	5.61E-02	3.86E-02	2.03E-02	9.54E-04	1.36E-04	1.30E-02	7.13E-08
Marine ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	2.09E+00	3.38E-01	2.89E-01	1.48E-01	1.45E-03	2.86E-04	3.82E-02	2.16E-07
Human carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	2.29E+00	2.61E-01	4.16E-01	1.11E-01	4.43E-03	1.36E-03	6.34E-01	1.48E-06
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity(kg 1.4-DCB)	2.10E+02	9.49E+00	1.11E+01	1.98E+00	1.26E-01	3.10E-02	7.90E+00	3.56E-05
Land use (m2a crop eq)	1.79E+00	1.41E-01	1.49E-01	6.09E-02	1.08E-02	1.78E-03	8.08E-02	1.48E-06
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu eq)	1.11E+01	2.96E-01	3.12E-01	1.40E-01	2.17E-04	9.56E-05	1.72E-01	3.02E-07
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	2.22E+01	1.50E+00	1.75E+00	4.79E-01	1.79E-01	2.12E-01	2.78E+00	3.73E-05
Water consumption (m3)	5.40E+00	4.80E-02	5.41E-02	1.51E-02	-2.77E-03	4.25E-03	7.62E-02	1.44E-04

Figure 35 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC622 battery pack (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

NMC811

Table 34 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Battery cells	BMS	Packaging	Electronic components	Electricity	Polymers	Precious metals	Water	Total
Global warming	1.24E+00	9.50E-02	1.27E-01	2.93E-02	1.40E-02	6.55E-03	2.28E-01	2.71E-06	1.74E+00
Stratospheric ozone depletion	3.21E-04	2.64E-05	2.41E-05	8.34E-06	2.39E-06	6.90E-07	2.54E-05	8.60E-10	4.08E-04
Ionizing radiation	1.34E-04	6.63E-06	4.62E-06	2.03E-06	1.26E-06	1.87E-07	2.80E-06	1.68E-10	1.51E-04
Ozone formation	1.19E-02	1.08E-03	1.35E-03	4.10E-04	7.04E-05	4.35E-05	1.85E-03	2.03E-08	1.67E-02
Fine particulate matter formation	3.07E+00	1.77E-01	2.31E-01	5.94E-02	1.11E-02	4.94E-03	3.05E-01	3.56E-06	3.86E+00
Terrestrial acidification	4.92E-02	2.21E-03	3.11E-03	7.81E-04	1.10E-04	5.91E-05	3.86E-03	3.31E-08	5.93E-02
Freshwater eutrophication,	1.90E-03	2.04E-04	1.40E-04	6.32E-05	1.74E-05	1.91E-06	8.34E-05	1.17E-09	2.41E-03
Marine eutrophication	2.87E-06	6.52E-08	5.52E-08	2.06E-08	3.62E-08	2.40E-09	2.65E-08	2.91E-13	3.07E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1.25E-02	4.05E-04	4.23E-04	5.33E-05	1.25E-06	6.91E-07	1.84E-04	7.61E-10	1.36E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	3.30E-05	1.05E-05	7.53E-06	3.81E-06	1.87E-07	2.81E-08	2.62E-06	1.43E-11	5.77E-05
Marine ecotoxicity	5.55E-05	9.59E-06	8.56E-06	4.23E-06	4.29E-08	8.80E-09	1.35E-06	6.57E-12	7.92E-05
Human carcinogenic toxicity	1.18E-01	1.45E-02	2.40E-02	6.17E-03	2.56E-04	8.10E-05	3.71E-02	8.77E-08	2.00E-01
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	7.77E-01	3.61E-02	4.39E-02	7.54E-03	5.02E-04	1.25E-04	3.50E-02	1.45E-07	9.00E-01
Land use	3.96E-03	3.37E-04	3.71E-04	1.46E-04	2.68E-05	4.66E-06	2.13E-04	3.79E-09	5.06E-03
Mineral resource scarcity	1.40E-02	4.90E-04	5.35E-04	2.31E-04	3.66E-07	1.70E-07	3.08E-04	5.34E-10	1.56E-02
Fossil resource scarcity	3.86E-02	2.36E-03	2.67E-03	7.93E-04	3.20E-04	5.96E-04	3.64E-03	5.73E-08	4.90E-02
Water consumption	1.52E-01	7.16E-04	9.90E-04	2.61E-04	-2.77E-04	1.72E-04	1.33E-03	6.24E-06	1.56E-01
Total	5.491963	0.330225	0.435888	0.10518	0.026147	0.012575	0.617114	1.29E-05	7.019105

Table 35 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery cell in Pt (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Anode	Battery separator	Cathode. NMC811	Copper	Electrolyte	Electricity	Polymers	Aluminium	Total
Global warming	1.25E-01	5.12E-02	7.15E-01	8.14E-02	6.07E-02	1.40E-01	9.18E-04	6.98E-02	1.24343
Stratospheric ozone depletion	2.43E-05	8.34E-06	2.02E-04	5.00E-05	8.27E-06	1.72E-05	2.47E-06	8.26E-06	0.000321
Ionizing radiation	3.38E-06	2.62E-06	1.16E-04	5.46E-06	2.36E-06	2.61E-06	1.86E-08	1.01E-06	0.000134
Ozone formation	1.85E-03	3.83E-04	5.55E-03	2.17E-03	4.32E-04	9.67E-04	5.97E-06	5.51E-04	0.011907
Fine particulate matter formation	6.31E-01	5.31E-02	1.22E+00	8.98E-01	7.52E-02	9.91E-02	6.05E-04	8.78E-02	3.067945
Terrestrial acidification	1.03E-02	5.50E-04	1.97E-02	1.53E-02	1.04E-03	1.22E-03	8.05E-06	1.09E-03	0.049188
Freshwater eutrophication,	8.96E-05	1.83E-05	1.38E-03	2.90E-04	7.66E-05	2.26E-05	2.88E-07	2.48E-05	0.001901
Marine eutrophication	5.99E-08	3.14E-09	2.52E-06	9.74E-08	1.70E-07	4.02E-09	2.52E-10	8.27E-09	2.87E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	2.66E-03	4.50E-06	3.05E-03	6.67E-03	8.03E-05	8.27E-06	3.01E-07	2.24E-05	0.012484
Freshwater ecotoxicity	4.38E-06	1.22E-07	1.42E-05	1.26E-05	7.83E-07	2.11E-07	5.91E-09	7.17E-07	3.3E-05
Marine ecotoxicity	1.15E-05	4.87E-08	1.38E-05	2.92E-05	4.90E-07	8.60E-08	2.51E-09	2.58E-07	5.55E-05
Human carcinogenic toxicity	2.28E-02	6.76E-04	2.44E-02	5.76E-02	1.35E-03	1.37E-03	1.51E-05	1.01E-02	0.118349
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	1.97E-01	1.78E-03	7.28E-02	4.87E-01	6.58E-03	3.93E-03	1.90E-05	7.88E-03	0.777127
Land use	7.00E-04	7.27E-05	1.38E-03	1.50E-03	1.49E-04	9.43E-05	6.33E-07	5.94E-05	0.003964
Mineral resource scarcity	5.74E-04	6.53E-07	1.16E-02	1.74E-03	7.46E-05	9.16E-07	9.18E-08	8.01E-05	0.014038
Fossil resource scarcity	4.70E-03	1.26E-03	2.35E-02	1.91E-03	2.78E-03	3.27E-03	8.66E-05	1.13E-03	0.038643
Water consumption	1.39E-03	2.79E-04	1.45E-01	3.80E-03	1.33E-03	2.45E-04	1.81E-05	4.56E-04	0.152437
Total	0.998136	0.10935	2.245665	1.557705	0.149823	0.250525	0.00168	0.179077	5.49196

Table 36 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack (numeric) (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

Impact category	Battery cells	BMS	Packaging	Electronic components	Energy	Polymers	Precious metals	Water
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	8.28E+01	8.76E+00	8.14E+00	1.90E+00	9.53E-01	1.77E+00	1.44E+01	1.71E-02
Stratospheric ozone depletion (kg CFC11 eq)	3.85E-05	3.81E-06	2.84E-06	9.80E-07	2.99E-07	4.22E-07	3.00E-06	3.85E-09
Ionizing radiation (kBq Co-60 eq)	8.17E+00	6.51E-01	3.95E-01	1.75E-01	1.25E-01	5.33E-02	2.24E-01	1.17E-03
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	2.56E-01	3.10E-02	2.75E-02	8.20E-03	1.76E-03	6.57E-03	3.81E-02	4.36E-05
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	3.10E-01	2.59E-02	2.29E-02	5.98E-03	1.35E-03	3.20E-03	2.99E-02	2.84E-05
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	2.64E-01	3.23E-02	2.87E-02	8.77E-03	1.83E-03	7.00E-03	3.87E-02	4.65E-05
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	8.96E-01	6.18E-02	5.64E-02	1.44E-02	2.54E-03	8.96E-03	6.90E-02	4.87E-05
Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq)	6.36E-02	1.13E-02	7.40E-03	3.03E-03	6.61E-04	7.57E-04	5.10E-03	7.12E-06
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	7.95E-03	4.41E-04	3.36E-04	1.08E-04	1.48E-04	1.22E-04	3.46E-04	4.61E-07
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	4.22E+03	2.65E+02	1.46E+02	2.12E+01	3.13E+00	6.54E+00	6.48E+01	2.56E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	3.53E+01	5.86E+00	3.57E+00	1.57E+00	9.68E-02	8.94E-02	1.41E+00	1.60E-03
Marine ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	4.57E+01	7.70E+00	4.75E+00	2.10E+00	1.27E-01	1.22E-01	1.80E+00	2.07E-03
Human carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	8.53E+00	2.16E+00	1.87E+00	5.22E-01	5.68E-02	2.71E-01	2.91E+00	1.02E-02
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity(kg 1.4-DCB)	6.12E+02	9.25E+01	5.78E+01	2.50E+01	1.98E+00	2.24E+00	1.85E+01	1.31E-02
Land use (m2a crop eq)	2.55E+00	5.38E-01	2.76E-01	1.07E-01	4.03E-02	5.66E-01	1.75E-01	3.35E-04
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu eq)	8.69E+00	4.13E-01	3.34E-01	1.43E-01	2.34E-03	1.91E-02	1.93E-01	2.63E-04
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	2.21E+01	2.12E+00	1.90E+00	5.03E-01	2.12E-01	5.93E-01	3.03E+00	4.35E-03
Water consumption (m3)	4.03E+00	7.46E-02	5.92E-02	1.60E-02	-1.93E-03	1.46E-02	8.33E-02	3.27E-04

Figure 36 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC811 battery pack (FU = 1 kWh) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

SPINMATE's cell components process results

NMC powder production

Table 37 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC powder fabrication in pt (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) (numeric).

Impact category	Solution Production	Mixing	Spray Pyrolysis	Calcination I	Annealing	Sieve
Global warming	0.8064563	0.000311	0.038892	0.062497	0.109364	0.004825
Stratospheric ozone depletion	0.0002823	6.26E-07	7.82E-05	0.000125	0.000164	1.98E-06
Ionizing radiation	0.0001307	2.79E-07	3.49E-05	5.59E-05	8.13E-05	1E-07
Ozone formation	0.0088978	1.06E-06	0.197394	0.001856	0.000431	1.49E-05
Fine particulate matter formation	7.0021919	8.34E-05	1.611711	0.030034	0.047291	0.001447
Terrestrial acidification	0.1276258	1.27E-06	0.062351	0.000772	0.000684	2.24E-05
Freshwater eutrophication,	0.0027427	1.43E-07	1.78E-05	2.85E-05	7E-05	7.45E-07
Marine eutrophication	5.137E-06	5E-11	6.25E-09	1E-08	1.7E-08	1.47E-09
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	0.0129622	2.79E-08	3.49E-06	5.58E-06	9.78E-06	6.19E-07
Freshwater ecotoxicity	8.498E-05	5.55E-10	6.93E-08	1.11E-07	2.24E-07	3.58E-08
Marine ecotoxicity	6.71E-05	2.69E-10	3.37E-08	5.39E-08	1.01E-07	1.13E-08
Human carcinogenic toxicity	0.0900698	1.12E-06	0.00014	0.000223	0.000622	7.4E-05
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	0.1186617	1.05E-05	0.001311	0.002098	0.003801	6.49E-05
Land use	0.0024811	4.57E-06	0.000571	0.000914	0.001269	1.7E-06
Mineral resource scarcity	0.0192186	2.75E-08	3.44E-06	5.5E-06	8.72E-06	1.39E-07
Fossil resource scarcity	0.0275711	5.15E-06	0.000644	0.001031	0.002059	0.000216
Water consumption	0.1573264	0.000492	0.061349	0.098493	0.126996	0.000229

Table 38 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC powder fabrication (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).

Impact categories	Solution Production	Mixing	Spray Pyrolysis	Calcination I	Annealing	Sieve
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	49.67022	0.019162	2.395254	3.849073	6.735564	0.297197
Stratospheric ozone depletion (kg CFC11 eq)	3.19E-05	7.07E-08	8.83E-06	1.41E-05	1.86E-05	2.23E-07
Ionizing radiation (kBq Co-60 eq)	0.92158	0.001971	0.246387	0.394219	0.573655	0.000706
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	0.173923	2.08E-05	2.062597	0.021322	0.008441	0.000283
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	0.668795	7.96E-06	0.116795	0.002557	0.004513	0.000138
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	0.179401	2.13E-05	6.482665	0.058265	0.008683	0.000304
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	2.22635	2.22E-05	1.46277	0.016599	0.011938	0.00039
Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq)	0.015124	7.87E-07	9.84E-05	0.000157	0.000387	4.11E-06
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	0.011153	1.09E-07	1.36E-05	2.18E-05	3.69E-05	3.18E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	4197.634	0.009048	1.131003	1.809605	3.173581	0.200934
Freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	0.4522	2.95E-06	0.000369	0.000591	0.001193	0.000191
Marine ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	2.361668	9.48E-06	0.001185	0.001897	0.003542	0.000398
Human carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	1.624325	2.02E-05	0.002523	0.004037	0.011238	0.001336
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	31.23402	0.00276	0.344986	0.551977	1.000276	0.017082
Land use (m2a crop eq)	1.033878	0.001906	0.238229	0.381166	0.529225	0.000709
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu eq)	11.64577	1.67E-05	0.002082	0.003331	0.005276	8.42E-05
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	13.30496	0.003232	0.403985	0.646376	1.338637	0.07792
Water consumption (m3)	4.090126	0.026879	3.348391	5.375778	6.83803	0.010218

Figure 37 - Contributions to each impact category for the NMC powder fabrication (FU = 1 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H)

Lithium-Metal anode production

Table 39 - Potential environmental impacts of Li-M anode production in mPt (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) (numerical).

Impact Category	Li deposition	Protective layer deposition
Global warming	4.61694281	0.191158749
Stratospheric ozone depletion	0.000386062	0.000121579
Ionizing radiation	0.000313113	0.000210954
Ozone formation	0.083062248	0.001069321
Fine particulate matter formation	4.03012377	0.447486865
Terrestrial acidification	0.084707505	0.006396106
Freshwater eutrophication,	0.001329593	0.000142065
Marine eutrophication	2.23984E-06	1.1152E-07
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	0.006143214	0.00061206
Freshwater ecotoxicity	4.83498E-05	5.387E-06
Marine ecotoxicity	3.22978E-05	3.38988E-06
Human carcinogenic toxicity	0.0763267	0.019489344
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	0.123191262	0.054106019
Land use	0.004604582	0.001864677
Mineral resource scarcity	0.008209814	0.000244419
Fossil resource scarcity	0.030637661	0.017904851
Water consumption	0.149477139	0.007986391

Table 40 - Contributions to each impact category of Li-M anode production (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).

Impact category	Li deposition	Protective layer deposition
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	0.258565	0.011382
Stratospheric ozone depletion (kg CFC11 eq)	2.02E-07	5.46E-10
Ionizing radiation (kBq Co-60 eq)	0.001693	3.43E-05
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	0.001535	1.87E-05
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	0.002648	7.99E-06
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	0.001568	2.06E-05
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	0.008028	2.36E-05
Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq)	0.000117	1.16E-07
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	5.98E-05	4.03E-08
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	60.76658	0.001146
Freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	0.001968	3E-06
Marine ecotoxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	0.029093	4.81E-06
Human carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	0.029956	3.75E-05
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity (kg 1.4-DCB)	3.627243	0.000262
Land use (m2a crop eq)	0.019285	2.68E-05
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu eq)	0.034203	3.79E-06
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	0.059509	0.009539
Water consumption (m3)	0.005091	0.000105

Figure 38 - Contributions to each impact category of Li-M anode production (FU = 25.148 of g) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H)

Cathode wet processing

Table 41 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 g) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Mixing	Coating	Drying	Calendaring	Cutting	Total
Global warming	0.810659	0.418407	1.206117	0.006348	0.044436	2.485968
Stratospheric ozone depletion	0.000368	0.000112	0.000325	1.71E-06	1.2E-05	0.000819
Ionizing radiation	0.000311	0.00021	0.000615	3.24E-06	2.27E-05	0.001162
Ozone formation	0.087703	0.003114	0.008972	4.72E-05	0.000331	0.100167
Fine particulate matter formation	3.858633	0.338652	0.967261	0.005091	0.035636	5.205273
Terrestrial acidification	0.082453	0.004817	0.013806	7.27E-05	0.000509	0.101658
Freshwater eutrophication,	0.001465	0.0001	0.000286	1.51E-06	1.05E-05	0.001863
Marine eutrophication	2.21E-06	8.66E-08	2.51E-07	1.32E-09	9.26E-09	2.56E-06
Land use	0.003238	0.001198	0.003496	1.84E-05	0.000129	0.00808
Mineral resource scarcity	0.008102	3.85E-05	8.99E-05	4.73E-07	3.31E-06	0.008235
Fossil resource scarcity	0.029474	0.016868	0.04913	0.000259	0.00181	0.09754
Water consumption	0.189724	0.009209	0.026853	0.000141	0.000989	0.226916
Total	5.072134	0.792727	2.276951	0.011984	0.083888	8.237684

Table 42 Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing (FU = 527.79 g) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).

Impact category	Mixing	Coating	Drying	Calendaring	Cutting	Total
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	50.14047	25.77010352	74.2859	0.390978	2.736849	153.3243051
Stratospheric ozone depletion (Kg CFC1111 eq)	0.000188	1.26304E-05	3.67E-05	1.93E-07	1.35E-06	0.000238805
Ionizing radiation (KBq Co-60 eq)	2.19584	1.480790247	4.339623	0.02284	0.159881	8.198974854
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	0.977631	0.060370132	0.173852	0.000915	0.006405	1.219173279
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	0.353294	0.032317998	0.092307	0.000486	0.003401	0.481805816
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	2.794408	0.063013726	0.181555	0.000956	0.006689	3.046621032
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	1.5921	0.084035944	0.240851	0.001268	0.008873	1.927128206
Freshwater eutrophication (kg P eq)	0.00808	0.00055274	0.00158	8.32E-06	5.82E-05	0.01027932
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	0.004802	0.000188332	0.000547	2.88E-06	2.01E-05	0.005560456
Land use m2a crop eq)	1.350197	0.499751365	1.45796	0.007673	0.053714	3.369296355
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu)	4.909576	0.02333222	0.054427	0.000286	0.002005	4.989626697
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	13.799	7.562087619	21.91592	0.115347	0.807429	44.19978481
Water consumption (m3)	8.237766	0.241780559	0.701109	0.00369	0.02583	9.210176394

Figure 39 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode wet processing in Pt (FU = 527.79 g) - ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H);

Cathode dry processing

Table 43 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing in Pt (FU = 0.3 kg) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Mixing	Coating	Drying	Total
Global warming	0.212703	0.172808	0.04267	0.428182
Stratospheric ozone depletion	0.000132	4.89E-05	1.23E-05	0.000194
Ionizing radiation	6.14E-05	2.12E-05	5.36E-06	8.8E-05
Ozone formation	0.041964	0.000532	0.000125	0.042621
Fine particulate matter formation	1.754181	0.050625	0.011301	1.816107
Terrestrial acidification	0.038576	0.000823	0.000189	0.039588
Freshwater eutrophication,	0.000581	0.000334	7.26E-05	0.000987
Marine eutrophication	1.05E-06	1.95E-08	3.9E-09	1.07E-06
Land use	0.001063	0.000353	8.79E-05	0.001504
Mineral resource scarcity	0.003868	6.59E-05	1.17E-06	0.003935
Fossil resource scarcity	0.006752	0.002461	0.000527	0.00974
Water consumption	0.089518	0.000426	6.96E-05	0.090014
Total	2.149402	0.228499	0.055061	2.432962

Table 44 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing (FU = 0.3 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) (numeric).

Impact category	Mixing	Extrusion	Coating	Total
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	14.73215	10.64309	2.628007	28.00323989
Stratospheric ozone depletion (Kg CFC1111 eq)	0.001143	5.52E-06	1.39E-06	0.001150372
Ionizing radiation (KBq Co-60 eq)	0.434846	0.149441	0.037803	0.622090467
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	0.456301	0.010388	0.00246	0.469148494
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	0.160017	0.004831	0.001078	0.165926581
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	1.353353	0.010722	0.002526	1.366600654
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	0.748953	0.014359	0.003294	0.766606831
Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq)	0.003204	0.001843	0.000401	0.005447021
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	0.00227	4.23E-05	8.49E-06	0.00232114
Land use m2a crop eq)	0.443361	0.147206	0.036667	0.627233889
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu)	2.343944	0.039888	0.00071	2.38454131
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	3.346312	2.672573	0.642487	6.661371993
Water consumption (m3)	3.961036	0.066916	0.016033	4.043985974

Figure 40 - Potential environmental impacts of cathode dry processing (FU = 0.3 kg) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

Electrolyte production

Table 45 - Potential environmental impacts of electrolyte production in Pt (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H).

Impact category	Solubilisation	Mixing	Coating	Total
Global warming	1.02E-03	4.88E-04	2.86E-05	0.001539
Stratospheric ozone depletion	4.76E-07	2.49E-07	4.79E-09	7.3E-07
Ionizing radiation	2.48E-06	1.24E-06	2.28E-08	3.75E-06
Ozone formation	6.20E-06	3.11E-06	1.62E-07	9.48E-06
Fine particulate matter formation	4.86E-04	3.68E-04	1.34E-05	0.000867
Terrestrial acidification	7.74E-06	5.84E-06	2.15E-07	1.38E-05
Freshwater eutrophication,	5.04E-07	1.90E-07	3.62E-09	6.98E-07
Marine eutrophication	7.90E-10	8.73E-10	9.25E-12	1.67E-09
Land use	3.68E-06	1.92E-06	3.99E-08	5.65E-06
Mineral resource scarcity	5.26E-07	3.37E-07	5.46E-09	8.69E-07
Fossil resource scarcity	7.00E-05	2.56E-05	3.66E-06	9.93E-05
Water consumption	1.09E-05	6.74E-06	9.83E-07	1.86E-05
Total	1.61E-03	9.01E-04	4.71E-05	0.002559

Table 46 - Potential environmental impacts of electrolyte production (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

Impact category	Solubilisation	Mixing	Coating	Total
Global warming (kg CO2 eq)	0.041467	0.014208214	0.000834	0.056509
Stratospheric ozone depletion (Kg CFC1111 eq)	8.11E-06	1.32999E-08	2.56E-10	8.13E-06
Ionizing radiation (KBq Co-60 eq)	0.008296	0.004147084	7.62E-05	0.01252
Ozone formation. Human health (kg NOx eq)	5.59E-05	2.84055E-05	1.44E-06	8.58E-05
Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM2.5 eq)	2.19E-05	1.66231E-05	6.03E-07	3.91E-05
Ozone formation. Terrestrial ecosystems (kg NOx eq)	5.98E-05	2.98461E-05	1.56E-06	9.12E-05
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO2 eq)	6.38E-05	4.81451E-05	1.77E-06	0.000114
Freshwater eutrophication, (kg P eq)	1.31E-06	4.96645E-07	9.46E-09	1.82E-06
Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)	8.13E-07	8.96981E-07	9.51E-09	1.72E-06
Land use m2a crop eq)	0.000727	0.000379321	7.87E-06	0.001114
Mineral resource scarcity (kg Cu)	0.000151	9.66532E-05	1.56E-06	0.000249
Fossil resource scarcity (kg oil eq)	0.012527	0.004879622	0.000598	0.018004
Water consumption (m3)	0.000998	0.000517679	1.42E-05	0.00153

Figure 41- Potential environmental impacts of electrolyte production (FU = 2.39 g of Electrolyte) (numerical) - ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).